

LIST OF APPENDICES

1. NESCent Year 5 Awards
2. Meetings Held at NESCent in Year 5
3. Current NESCent Funded Groups Anticipated to Meet In Year 6
4. Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists at the Center In Year 5
5. Current Positions of Postdoctoral Fellow Completing NESCent Funding in Year 1-5
6. Participant List for Year 5
7. Student Interns
8. Demographics of NESCent Activities
 - a. Postdoctoral Fellows: Number of applications, applicants awards accepted/declined, applicants not approved (gender, residency [based on home institution], ethnicity, race, and citizenship)
 - b. Applicant Data for Scholars: Number of applications, applicants awards accepted/declined, applicants not approved (gender, residency [based on home institution], ethnicity, race, and citizenship)
 - c. Applicant Data for Groups (including PI's and co-PI's): Number of applications, applicants awards accepted/declined, applicants not approved (gender, residency [based on home institution], ethnicity, race, and citizenship)
 - d. Summary Award Data for Scholars and Groups (including PI's and co-PI's): gender, residency (based on home institution), ethnicity, race, and citizenship
 - e. Participant Data: gender, residency (based on home institution), ethnicity, race, and citizenship
 - f. Home Institution Type of Funded Participants
 - g. Attendees at NESCent Meeting by Geographic Location (maps)
9. Outreach
 - a. Website Traffic
 - b. Press Coverage for Year 5
 - c. NESCent Seminar Series for Year 5
 - d. Outreach Activities of Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists at the Center
10. NESCent Center Products (Publications, Software/Databases, Grants) for Year 5

Appendix 1: NESCent year 5 awards (12/1/08-11/30/09)

Principal and Co- Investigators	Institution of Principal and Co- Investigators	Project Name
Postdoctoral Fellows		
Julie Meachen-Samuels	University of California-Los Angeles	Competition, Guild Structure and Evolution in the Carnivora
Benjamin Redelings	North Carolina State University	Improved Probabilistic Models of Insertion/Deletion for Phylogenetic Inference
Liam Revell	Harvard University	Process and Pattern in the Phylogenetic Analysis of Comparative Data
Juan Santos	University of Texas-Austin	Multivariate Evolutionary Analysis: Integrating Structural Equation Modeling and Phylogenetics
Eric Schuettpeiz	Duke University	A Phylogenetic Approach to Understanding the Evolution of the Earth's Biomes
Gregor Yanega	North Carolina State University at Raleigh	A Comparative Phylogenetic Approach to the Study of Insular Avian Phenotypes
Long-term Sabbaticals		
James Hunt	North Carolina State University at Raleigh	The Evolution of Sociality
Michael Rosenberg	Arizona State University at the Tempe Campus	Geography, Phylogeny, and Population: An Evolutionary Synthesis
John Logsdon	University of Iowa	Sex, cells: An Evolutionary inquiry Into Sexual Reproduction
Short Term Scholars		
Travis Ingram	University of British Columbia	Divergence on Multiple Niche Axes During Adaptive Radiation: An Evolutionary Metacommunity Simulation Model
Roy Plotnick	University of Illinois at Chicago	Movement Paleocology, Trace Fossils, and the Evolution of Behavior
Lennart Olsson	Jena University	The Origin of Evolutionary Novelities in Amphibian Head Development
Frans Plooi	International Research-institute on Infant Studies	Translation of Field Notes for Developmental Study of Chimpanzee Vocal Communication

Appendix 1 cont.: NESCent year 5 awards

Triangle Scholars		
Susan Alberts	Duke University	Database enhancement and investigation of paternal and hybridization effects in a wild mammal population
Andy Deans	North Carolina State University	Using ontologies to enhance descriptive taxonomy and morphological phylogenetics
Working Groups		
Alexei Drummond, Marc Suchard, Andrew Rambaut	University of Auckland, University of California-Los Angeles, University of Edinburgh	Software for Bayesian Evolutionary Analysis by Sampling Trees
Margaret Hall, Christopher Heesy, Andrew Iwaniuk	Midwestern University, Midwestern University, Canadian Centre for Behavioural Neuroscience	Evolutionary Shifts in Vertebrate Visual Ecology and Visual System Morphology
Carl Schlichting, Courtney Murren	University of Connecticut, College of Charleston	Costs of Phenotypic Plasticity and Adaptation to Novel Environments
Albert Uy, Rebecca Safran	Syracuse University, University of Colorado at Boulder	An Integrative Evolutionary Approach to Examine Sexual Selection as a Mechanism of Speciation
Kathleen Donohue, Rafael Rubio de Casas	Duke University, Duke University	Germination, Trait Coevolution, and Niche Limits in Changing Environments
Stephen Smith, Nicolas Salamin, Erika Edwards	NESCent, University of Lausanne, Brown University	Grass Phylogeny Working Group II: Inferring the Complex History of C4 Photosynthesis in Grasses
Norman Johnson, Louise Mead, James Smith	University of Massachusetts-Amherst, National Center for Science Education, Michigan State University	Communicating the Relevance of Human Evolution

Appendix 1 cont.: NESCent year 5 awards

Catalysis Meetings		
David Sloan Wilson	The State University of New York at Binghamton	<u>The Nature of Regulation: How Evolutionary Theory Can Inform the Regulation of Large-Scale Human Social Interactions</u>
Alan Jones, Jotun Hein, Joe Thorton, Etsuko Moriyama	University of North Carolina, Oxford University, University of Oregon, University of Nebraska	<u>Evolution of G Protein Coupled Signaling: Lineages, Constraints, and Tempo</u>
Rob Guralnick, Jessica Metcalf, Alan Cooper	University of Colorado at Boulder, University of Adelaide, University of Adelaide	<u>Integrating Datasets to investigate Megafaunal Extinction in the Late Quaternary</u>

Appendix 2: Courses and catalysis, working group, science advisory board, and hosted meetings held at NESCent in year 5 (12/1/08-11/30/09)

Dates	Group Leaders	Title	Attendees	Type of Meeting
1/6/2009- 1/9/2009	Fenster, Charles Armbruster, William	Floral Assembly: Quantifying the Composition of a Complex Adaptive Structure	14	Working Group
1/11/09- 1/15/09	Susan Alberts Karen Strier	Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories	10	Working Group
1/30/2009- 2/2/2009	Kowalewski, Michal Payne, Jonathan Stempien, Jennifer	Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology	12	Working Group
2/5/09- 2/6/09	Kingsolver, Joel	Science Advisory Board	15	Science Advisory Board Meetings
2/26/2009- 2/28/2009	German, Rebecca Vinyard, Chris Williams, Susan Wall, Christine	Analysis and Synthesis of Physiologic Data from the Mammalian Feeding Apparatus	19	Working Group
3/9/2009- 3/13/2009	Lapp, Hilmar Vision, Todd Stoltzfus, Arlin Vos, Rutger	NESCent Database Interoperability Hackathon	24	Informatics Working Group
3/19/2009- 3/21/2009	Robbins, Peter Beall, Cynthia	Human Evolution and Adaptation to High-Altitude Hypoxia	23	Catalysis Meeting
4/1/2009- 4/3/2009	Richards, Christina Bossdorf, Oliver Pigliucci, Massimo	What Role, if any, Does Heritable Epigenetic Variation Play in Phenotypic Evolution?	27	Catalysis Meeting
4/9/2009- 4/11/2009	Edwards, Erika Stromberg, Caroline Osborne, Colin	Toward A New Synthesis of the Evolutionary History & Ecology of C4 Grasses	24	Catalysis Meeting
4/10/2009- 4/12/2009	Kramer, Elena Hodges, Scott	Building tools for emerging model systems in Development, Evolution, and Ecology	15	Working Group
4/27/2009- 4/30/2009	Mabee, Paula Vision, Todd Westerfield, Monte	Evolutionary Ontologies Workshop	20	Informatics Working Group
5/7/2009- 5/8/2009	Sanderson, Mike Jorgenson, Rich	iPlant: Phylogeny GC Team Meeting (IPTOL)	16	Hosted Meeting

Appendix 2 cont.: Meetings Held at NESCent in Year 5

5/8/2009- 5/9/2009	Uno, Gordon Scotchmoor, Judy	Evolution across the curriculum	6	EOG Working Group
5/14/2009- 5/15/2009	Mackay, Trudy Stearns, Stephen Govindaraju, Diddahally	Measuring Evolutionary Change in Modern Human Populations	9	Working Group
5/19/2009- 5/21/2009	Pfennig, David Moczek, Armin	Evolution and Development of Polyphenisms: Pathways to Innovation and Diversification	12	Working Group
5/21/2009- 5/22/2009	Vision, Todd Schaeffer, Peggy	Dryad Management Board Meeting	23	Informatics Working Group
5/22/2009- 5/24/2009	Lahti, David	Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution	7	Working Group
5/26/2009- 5/29/2009	Graham, Catherine Rahbek, Carsten Kozak, Ken	Montane Diversity in Space and Time: Linking Evolutionary Biology and Macroecology	15	Working Group
5/30/2009- 6/2/2009	Fenster, Charles Armbruster, William	Floral assembly: Quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure	9	Working Group
6/29/09- 7/1/09	Weintraub, Jenkins	EOG Teacher Workshop: Evolution 2009	16	Workshop
7/6/2009- 7/9/2009	Hall, Margaret Heesy, Christopher Iwaniuk, Andrew	Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology	15	Working Group
7/6/2009- 7/10/2009	Gurevitch, Jessica Lajeunesse, Marc Mengersen, Kerrie	An Introduction to Meta-analysis in Ecology and Evolutionary Biology	26	Informatics Course
7/16/2009- 7/19/2009	Clements, David	GMOD Summer School	35	Informatics Course
7/17/2009- 7/18/20a09	Gudelj, Ivana Forde, Samantha	Mathematical Models, Microbes & Evolutionary Diversification	11	Working Group
8/10/2009- 8/13/2009	Meichner, William Allard, Suzi Wilson, Bruce Vision, Todd	Virtual Data Center for Earth Observations Coordination Meeting	21	Hosted Meeting
8/10/2009- 8/14/2009	German, Rebecca Vinyard, Chris Williams, Susan Wall, Christine	Analysis and Synthesis of Physiologic Data from the Mammalian Feeding Apparatus, PI Meeting	4	
9/9/2009- 9/11/2009	Schlichting, Carl Murren, Courtney	Costs of Phenotypic Plasticity and Adaptation to Novel Environments	14	Working Group
9/9/2009-	Wiegmann, Brian	Future Directions in	29	Hosted

Appendix 2 cont.: Meetings Held at NESCent in Year 5

9/11/2009	Herendeen, Patrick	Systematics		Meeting
9/10/2009- 9/11/2009	Kingsolver, Joel	NESCent Advisory Board	15	Science Advisory Board Meetings
9/24/2009- 9/26/2009	Donovan, Sam	Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education EOG TREE	11	EOG Working Group
10/1/2009- 10/2/2009	Hofmann, Gretchen	Evolution and Global Change in the Oceans Workshop	15	Hosted Meeting
10/2/2009- 10/6/2009	Uy, Albert Safran, Rebecca	An Integrative Evolutionary Approach to Examine Sexual Selection as a Mechanism of Speciation	17	Working Group
10/6/2009- 10/7/2009	Jenkins, Kristin	Synthesis Center Education and Outreach	16	EOG Working Group
10/9/2009- 10/12/2009	Payne, Jonathan Kowalewski, Michal Stempien, Jennifer	Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology - Working Group Summary	28	Working Group
10/12/2009- 10/15/2009	Drummond, Alexei Suchard, Marc Rambaut, Andrew	Software for Bayesian Evolutionary Analysis by Sampling Trees	14	Working Group
11/13/2009- 11/16/2009	Wilson, David Sloan	The Nature of Regulation: How Evolutionary Theory Can Inform the Regulation of Large-Scale Human Social Interactions	30	Catalysis Meeting
10/16/2009- 10/18/2009	Pfennig, David Moczek, Armin	Evolution and Development of Polyphenisms: Pathways to Innovation and Diversification	13	Working Group
10/24/2009- 10/28/2009	Tewksbury, Joshua Holt, Robert Buckley, Lauren Angilletta, Michael	Mechanistic Distribution Models: Energetics, Fitness, and Population Dynamics	17	Working Group
11/19/2009- 11/20/2009	Hare, Brian Nunn, Charles	How Does Cognition Evolve?	14	Working Group

Appendix 3: NESCent funded catalysis and working groups anticipated to meet in year 6 (12/1/09-11/30/10)

Title	Group Leaders	Group Type
Evolution of G Protein Coupled Signaling: Lineages, Constraints, and Tempo	Jones, Hein, Moriyama, Thorton	Catalysis Group
Integrating Datasets to Investigate Megafaunal Extinction in the Late Quaternary	Metcalf, Cooper, Guralnick	Catalysis Group
Evolution Across the Curriculum	Scotchmoor, Uno	Education/Outreach Group
How Does Cognition Evolve?	Nunn, Hare	Working Group
Montane Diversity in Space and Time: Linking Evolutionary Biology and Macroecology	Graham, Kozack, Rahbek	Working Group
Measuring Evolutionary Change in Modern Human Populations Using Cohort Data	Stearns, Mackay, Clark, Govindaraju	Working Group
Genetic Monitoring: Development of Tools for Conservation and Management	Allendorf, Schwartz	Working Group
Floral Assembly: Quantifying the Composition of a Complex Adaptive Structure	Fenster, Armbruster	Working Group
Evolution and Development of Polyphenisms: Pathways to Innovation and Diversification	Moczek, Pfennig	Working Group
Analysis and Synthesis of Physiologic Data from the Mammalian Feeding Apparatus	German, Vinyard, Wall, Williams	Working Group
Software for Bayesian Evolutionary Analysis by Sampling Trees	Suchard, Drummond, Rambaut	Working Group
Evolutionary shifts in Vertebrate Visual Ecology and Visual System Morphology	Iwaniuk, Heesy, Hall	Working Group
Costs of Phenotypic Plasticity and Adaptation to Novel Environments	Murren, Schlichting	Working Group
An Integrative Evolutionary Approach to Examine Sexual Selection as a Mechanism of Speciation	Uy, Safran	Working Group
Germination, Trait Coevolution, and Niche Limits in Changing Environments	Donohue, Rubio de Casas	Working Group
Toward A New Synthesis of the Evolutionary History and Ecology of C4 Grasses	Osborne, Edwards, Stromberg	Working Group
Communicating the Relevance of Human Evolution	Johnson, Smith, Mead	Working Group

Appendix 4: Postdoctoral fellows, sabbatical scholars, and short-term visitors at the center in year 5 (12/1/08-12/1/09). For Postdoctoral fellows institution refers to prior institution before joining NESCent. Open-ended dates are given for scientists continuing into year 6 (12/1/09-12/1/10)

Name	Institution	Project	Dates
Long-term Sabbatical Scholars (5)			
Gilchrist, George	College of William and Mary	The Evolution of Performance Curves in Seasonal Environments	8/1/08-9/6/09
d' Orgiex, Stephen	Virginia State University	Evolution Courses, Mountaintop Lizards and a View Toward the Future Research	9/1/08-5/31/09
Antolin, Michael	Colorado State University	Sabbatical Book Project: Genetics of Small Populations	9/15/08-5/15/09
Hunt, James	North Carolina State University at Raleigh	The Evolution of Sociality	9/1/09-
Rosenberg, Michael	Arizona State University at the Tempe Campus	Geography, Phylogeny, and Population: An Evolutionary Synthesis	9/1/09-
Postdoctoral Fellows (17)			
Hazkani-Covo, Einat	Tel-Aiv University	Numt Variation in Metazoan Genomes: Gain, Loss, Duplication and Possible Function	6/1/06-5/31/09
Sidlauskas, Brian	University of Chicago	Understanding Parallel Morphological Diversification in Sister Fish Faunas	9/1/06-5/31/09
Ganapathy, Ganesh	University of Texas at Austin	New DCM Methods for ML, and Pattern Identification in Biogeography	12/1/06
O'Meara, Brian	University of California-Davis	Methods to Examine Trait Evolution on Trees: Advancing the Field	11/1/07-7/31/09
Spaeth, Paula	Stanford University	Competition and Meso-Evolutionary Change in the Mammalian Fossil Record	12/1/07-6/26/09
McCall, Lauren	University of Cambridge	Building a Framework for the Study of Cultural Evolution	12/1/07-
Lajeunesse, Marc	Cornell University	Meta-Analysis and the Comparative Phylogenetic Method	9/1/08-
Smith, Stephen	Yale University	Integrating Species Distribution Modeling and Phylogenetics	10/1/08-
Botero, Carlos	Cornell University	Evolution of Conventional Signals: From Individuals to Populations and Back	1/1/09-
Meachen-Samuels, Julie	University of California-Los Angeles	Competition, Guild Structure and Evolution in the Carnivora	8/1/09-
Revell, Liam	Harvard University	Process and Pattern in the Phylogenetic Analysis of Comparative dDta	8/1/09-
Schuettpelz, Eric	Duke University	A Phylogenetic Approach to Understanding the Evolution of the Earth's Biomes	8/1/09-
Yanega, Gregor	North Carolina State University at Raleigh	A Comparative Phylogenetic Approach to the Study of Insular Avian Phenotypes	8/1/09-
Roberts, Trina	University of Alaska	Sticky Tips and Misplaced Roots: Is there a	8/1/09-

	Fairbanks	Bias in Intraspecific Phylogenetics?	
Redelings, Benjamin	North Carolina State University	Improved Probabilistic Models of Insertion/Deletion for Phylogenetic Inference	9/1/09-
Auld, Josh	University of Pittsburgh-Main Campus	Evaluating the Effects of Inbreeding on Dispersal	10/1/09-
Santos, Juan	University of Texas-Austin	Multivariate Evolutionary Analysis: Integrating Structural Equation Modeling and Phylogenetics	10/1/09-

Short-term Visitors (10)

Gurevitch, Jessica	SUNY at Stony Brook	Toward a General Theory of Biological Invasions	1/9/09-1/16/09
Fox, Gordon	University of South Florida	Toward a General Theory of Biological Invasions	1/12/09-1/16/09
Singh, Inderjit	University of Delhi	Toward a General Theory of Biological Invasions	1/12/09-1/16/09
Taub, Daniel	Southwestern University	Toward a General Theory of Biological Invasions	1/12/09-1/16/09
Wardle, Glenda	University of Sydney	Toward a General Theory of Biological Invasions	1/12/09-1/16/09
Hamrick, James	University of Georgia	Toward a General Theory of Biological Invasions	1/12/09-1/16/09
Singh, Inderjit	University of Delhi	Toward a General Theory of Biological Invasions	1/12/09-1/16/09
Alfaro, Michael	Washington State University	Integrating Fossil and Molecular Data in the Study of Diversification	2/16/09-2/20/09
Harmon, Luke	University of Idaho	Integrating Fossil and Molecular Data in the Study of Diversification	2/16/09-2/20/09
Hunt, Gene	Smithsonian Institution	Integrating Fossil and Molecular Data in the Study of Diversification	2/16/09-2/20/09

Science and Policy			
Visiting Scientists Without Funding			
Peet, Robert	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	Application of Taxon Concepts in Biodiversity Informatics	7/1/08-8/1/09
At-Large Members of the Operations Committee			
Pfennig, David	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	N/A	7/1/09-
Roth, Louise	Duke University	N/A	6/1/09-
Thorne, Jeff	North Carolina State University	N/A	1/1/09-

Appendix 5: Current positions of postdoctoral fellows completing NESCent funding in years 1-5 (12/1/04-11/30/09)

Name	Professional Role	Institution	NESCent End Date
Burleigh, Gordon	Assistant Professor	Florida State University	8/15/08
Fisher, Kirsten	Assistant Professor	California State University, Los Angeles	8/31/08
Ganapathy, Ganesh	Postdoctoral Fellow	Duke University	11/30/09
Granek, Joshua	Postdoctoral Fellow	Duke University	7/31/07
Hazkani-Covo, Einat	Postdoctoral Fellow	Duke University	5/31/09
Hereford, Joe	Postdoctoral Fellow	University of Maryland	12/15/06
Hoeksema, Jason	Assistant Professor	University of Mississippi	7/31/07
Hopkins, Samantha	Assistant Professor	University of Oregon	8/31/07
Kidd, David	Research Associate	Imperial College of London	8/31/08
O'Meara, Brian	Assistant Professor	University of Tennessee	7/31/09
Price, Samantha	Postdoctoral Fellow	University of California, Davis	10/31/08
Sidlauskas, Brian	Assistant Professor	Oregon State University	6/30/09
Spaeth, Paula	Assistant Professor	Northland College	7/31/09
Zanne, Amy	Assistant Professor	University of Missouri, St. Louis	4/30/08
Zwicky, Derrick	Postdoctoral Fellow	University of Kansas	4/30/08

Appendix 6: NESCent Participant List for Year 5

Catalysis Meetings

March 19 - 21, 2009

Human Evolution and Adaptation to High-Altitude Hypoxia

Coordinators: Cynthia M. Beall
Peter Robbins

Participants:

Gail Henderson
Theodore Garland
Changqing Zeng
Gianpiero Cavalleri
Tom Brutsaert
Thelma Baker
Almaz Aldashev
Patrick Sullivan
Mike Weale
Jeff Wall
Kathleen (Katrina) Voss
Enrique Vargas
Jay F. Storz
Mark Shriver
Kevin Shianna
Yannis Pitsiladis
Simon R Myers
Lorna Moore
Hugh E. Montgomery
Fabiola Leon-Velarde
Amha Gebremedhin
Cynthia M. Beall
Peter Robbins

Institutions:

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
University of California-Riverside
Beijing Institute of Genomics
Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland
Albany University
Pennsylvania State University-College of Medicine
National Center for Cardiology, Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
King's College London
University of California-San Francisco
The Pennsylvania State University
IBBA, La Paz, Bolivia
University of Nebraska at Kearney
Pennsylvania State University
Duke University
University of Glasgow
Oxford University
Wake Forest University
University College, London, UK
University Cayetano Heredia, Peru
Addis Ababa University
Case Western Reserve University
University of Oxford

April 1 - 3, 2009

What Role, If Any, Does Heritable Epigenetic Variation Play in Phenotypic Evolution?

Coordinators: Christina L. Richards
Oliver Bossdorf
Massimo Pigliucci

Participants:

Frank Johannes
Troy Day
Jonathan Wendel
Reiner Veitia
Armel Salmon
Douglas Ruden
David Rosenthal
Eric Richards
Michael Purugganan
John Nason

Institutions:

University Groningen
Queen's University
Iowa State University
Université Paris Diderot, France
Iowa State University
Wayne State University
Institute for Genomic Biology, University of Illinois
Boyce Thompson Institute, Cornell University
New York University
Iowa State University

Pawel Michalak
Sasha Levy
John Kelley
Eva Jablonka
Frederic Hospital
Liza Holeski
Diane Genereux
Mary Ann Fieldes
Tamara Davis
David Crews
Vincent Colot
Amy Bouck
James Birchler
Malika Ainouche
Christina L. Richards
Oliver Bossdorf
Massimo Pigliucci

University of Texas- Arlington
New York University
University of Kansas
Tel Aviv University, Israel
INRA, France
University of Wisconsin
University of Washington
Wilfrid Laurier University, Canada
Bryn Mawr College
University of Texas- Austin
Ecole Normale Supérieure, France
Pioneer Hi-Bred International, Inc.
University of Missouri
University of Rennes, France
New York University
University of Bern
SUNY at Stony Brook

April 9 - 11, 2009

Toward A New Synthesis of the Evolutionary History and Ecology of C4 Grasses

Coordinators: Erika J. Edwards
Caroline A. E. Stromberg
Colin Osborne

Participants:

Andrew Leakey
David Nelson
Rowan Sage
Jeffery M. Saarela
Benjamin Passey
Asaph Cousins
David Fox
Rob Freckleton
Oula Ghannoum
James Hartwell
Christine M Janis
Jon Keeley
Alan Knapp
Brett Tipple
Erika J Edwards
Caroline A. E. Stromberg
Colin Osborne
Yongsong Huang
Christopher Still
Nicolas Salamin
Osvaldo Sala
Stephen Smith
William Bond
Pascal-Antoine Christin

Institutions:

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
University of Toronto
Canadian Museum of Nature
California Institute of Technology
Washington State University
University of Minnesota
University of Sheffield
University of Western Sydney
University of Liverpool
Brown University
University of California - Los Angeles
Colorado State University
Yale University
Brown University
University of Washington-Seattle Campus
University of Sheffield
Brown University
University of California-Santa Barbara
Universite de Lausanne
Brown University
NESCent
University of Cape Town
University of Lausanne

November 13 - 16, 2009

The Nature of Regulation: How Evolutionary Theory Can Inform the Regulation of Large-Scale Human Social Interactions

Coordinator: David Sloan Wilson

Participants:

Joe Henrich
Stephen Hubbell
Robert Kadar
Douglas Kenrick
Janet Landa
Jerry Lieberman
Andrew Lo
Guru Madhavan
Joel Peck
Peter J. Richerson
Peter Todd
Peter Turchin
Jonathan Turner
Harvey Whitehouse
Edward O. Wilson
Bernard Winograd
Antony Adolf
Robert Axtell
Jenna Bednar
Eric Beinhocker
Anthony Biglan
Fred Blum
Colin Camerer
Terrence Deacon
Jim DeVona
Jennifer Fewell
Oliver Goodenough
Patricia Gowaty
Avner Greif
Peter Hammerstein
David Sloan Wilson

Institutions:

University of British Columbia
University of California - Los Angeles
Binghamton University
Arizona State University
York University
Humanists of Florida Association
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
National Academy of Sciences
University of Sussex
University of California - Davis
Indiana University
University of Connecticut
University of California - Riverside
Oxford University
Harvard University
Prudential Financial, Inc.
Independent scholar
George Mason University
University of Michigan
McKinsey Global Institute
Oregon Research Institute
California Institute of Technology
California Institute of Technology
University of California - Berkeley
Binghamton University
Arizona State University
Vermont Law School
University of California - Los Angeles
Stanford University
Humboldt University, Berlin
SUNY at Binghamton

Working Groups

January 6 - 9, 2009

Floral Assembly: Quantifying the Composition of a Complex Adaptive Structure

Coordinators: William Scott Armbruster
Charles Fenster

Participants:

Michael Alfaro
Lawrence Harder
Christopher Hardy
Lena C. Hileman
Larry Hufford
Amy Litt
Susana Magallon
Brian Moore
Peter Stevens
Pamela K. Diggle
William Scott Armbruster
Charles Fenster
Brian C. O'Meara

Institutions:

University of California-Los Angeles
University of Calgary
Millersville State University
University of Kansas Main Campus
Washington State University
New York Botanical Garden
Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico
University of California-Berkeley
University of Missouri-St. Louis
University of Colorado at Boulder
University of Alaska Fairbanks
University of Maryland-University College
NESCent

January 7 - 10, 2009

Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories

Coordinators: Karen B. Strier
Susan C. Alberts

Participants:

Jeanne Altmann
Diane K. Brockman
Anne Bronikowski
Marina Cords
Linda M. Fedigan
Bill Morris
Anne Pusey
Tara Stoinski
Karen B. Strier
Susan C. Alberts

Institutions:

Princeton University
University of North Carolina at Charlotte
Iowa State University
Columbia University in the City of New York
University of Calgary
Duke University
University of Minnesota-Twin Cities
Zoo Atlanta and Dian Fossey Gorilla Fund
University of Wisconsin Colleges
Duke University

January 30 - 2, 2009

Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology

Coordinators: Michal Kowalewski
Jennifer Stempien
Jonathan Payne

Participants:

Alison G. Boyer
Seth Finnegan
Richard Krause
Sara Lyons
Craig R. McClain
Daniel McShea

Institutions:

University of California-San Diego
Stanford University
Humboldt University
Smithsonian Institutions
NESCent
Duke University

Philip Novack-Gottshall
Felisa A. Smith
Paula Spaeth
Michal Kowalewski
Jennifer Stempien
Jonathan Payne

University of West Georgia
University of New Mexico-Main Campus
NESCent
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State Univ
University of Colorado at Boulder
Stanford University

February 26 - 28, 2009

Analysis and Synthesis of Physiologic Data from the Mammalian Feeding Apparatus

Coordinators: Rebecca Z. German
Chris Vinyard
Susan Williams
Christine Wall

Participants:

Rebecca Z. German
Chris Vinyard
Susan Williams
Christine Wall
Elizabeth L. Brainerd
Alfred W. Crompton
Frits De Vree
Alison Doherty
Robert Druzinsky
Vladimir Gapeyev
Caroline J. Harper
Susan W. Herring
Bill Hylander
Nicolai Konow
Geerling E.J. Langenbach
Dan Lieberman
Keith Metzger
Callum Ross
Kathleen K. Smith

Institutions:

Johns Hopkins University
Northeastern Ohio Universities College of Medicine
Ohio State University-Main Campus
Duke University
Brown University
Harvard University
University of Antwerp
Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of Medicine
Governors State University
NESCent
Brown University
University of Washington-Bothell Campus
Duke University
John Hopkins University
University of Amsterdam
Harvard University
Touro College
University of Chicago
NESCent

April 10 - 12, 2009

Building tools for emerging model systems in Development, Evolution, and Ecology

Coordinators: Elena M. Kramer
Scott Hodges

Participants:

David Clements
Cassandra Extavour
Bob Freeman
Vladimir Gapeyev
Andrew Groover
Chris Lowe
Antónia Monteiro
Christos Noutsos
Brant Peterson
Adam Reitzel
Mike Shapiro
Todd Vision

Institutions:

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Harvard University
Harvard Medical School
NESCent
Forest Service
University of Chicago
Yale University
University of Chicago
Harvard University
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institutions
University of Utah
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

John Willis
Elena M. Kramer
Scott Hodges

Duke University
Harvard University
University of California-Santa Barbara

May 14 - 15, 2009

Measuring Evolutionary Change in Modern Human Populations

Coordinators: Stephen Stearns
Trudy Mackay
Diddahally Govindaraju

Participants:

Stephen Stearns
Trudy Mackay
Diddahally Govindaraju
Douglas Ewbank
Sean Byars
Charles J Goodnight
Joseph Massaro
Shamil Sunyaev
Anatoliy Yashin

Institutions:

Yale University
North Carolina State University at Raleigh
Boston University
University of Pennsylvania
Yale University
University of Vermont
Boston University School of Public Health
Brigham & Women's Hospital and Harvard Medical
Duke University

May 19 - 21, 2009

Evolution and Development of Polyphenisms: Pathways to Innovation and Diversification

Coordinators: David Pfennig
Armin Moczek

Participants:

David Pfennig
Matthew Wund
Mary Jane West-Eberhard
Sonia E. Sultan
Emilie Snell-Rood
Carl Schlichting
Cris C. Ledon-Rettig
Susan Foster
Ian Dworkin
Tami Cruickshank
Ehab Abouheif
Armin Moczek

Institutions:

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Clark University
Smithsonian Institutions
Wesleyan University
University of Indiana
University of Connecticut
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Clark University
Michigan State University
University of Indiana
McGill University
Indiana University-Bloomington

May 22 - 24, 2009

Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution

Coordinators: David Lahti

Participants:

Josh Mackie
Ted Stankowich
Norman Johnson
Susan Foster
Kathleen Donohue
Richard G. Coss
David Lahti

Institutions:

San Jose State University
University of Massachusetts Amherst
University of Massachusetts
Clark University
Duke University
University of California - Davis
University of Massachusetts Amherst

May 26 - 29, 2009

Montane Diversity in Space and Time: Linking Evolutionary Biology and Macroecology

Coordinators: Carsten Rahbek
Ken Kozak
Catherine Graham

Participants:

Carsten Rahbek
Ken Kozak
Catherine Graham
Kelly Zamudio
Jeremy VanDerWal
Christopher Schneider
Nathan Sanders
Juan L. Parra
Craig Moritz
Madhava Meegaskumbura
Christy McCain
Ana Carnaval
Carlos Daniel Cadena
Rauri Bowie
Trina E Roberts

Institutions:

University of Copenhagen
University of Minnesota-Twin Cities
SUNY at Stony Brook
Cornell University
James Cook University
Boston University
University of Tennessee - Knoxville
Stony Brook University
University of California - Berkeley
Harvard University
University of Colorado - Boulder
University of California - Berkeley
Universidad de los Andes
University of California - Berkeley
NESCent

May 30 - 2, 2009

Floral assembly: Quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure

Coordinators: William Scott Armbruster
Charles Fenster

Participants:

Stephen Smith
Stacy Smith
Amy Litt
Larry Hufford
Christopher Hardy
Lawrence Harder
Pamela K Diggle
William Scott Armbruster
Charles Fenster

Institutions:

NESCent
Duke University
New York Botanical Garden
Washington State University
Millersville University
University of Calgary
University of Colorado; National Science Foundation
University of Portsmouth
University of Maryland-University College

July 6 - 9, 2009

Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology

Coordinators: Margaret Hall
Christopher Heesy
Andrew Iwaniuk

Participants:

Margaret Hall
Christopher Heesy
Andrew Iwaniuk
Kara Yopak
Doug Wong-Wylie
Eric Warrant
Saul Nava
Gillian Moritz

Institutions:

Midwestern University
Midwestern University
University of Lethbridge
University of California, San Diego
University of Alberta, Canada
University of Lund, Sweden
Indiana University
University of California, Santa Cruz

Thomas Lisney
Harvey Karten
Jason Kamilar
Esteban Fernandez-Juricic
Nathaniel Dominy
Shaun P. Collin
Olaf RP Bininda-Emonds

Uppsala University, Sweden
University of California, San Diego
Washington University
Purdue University
University of California, Santa Cruz
University of Queensland, Australia
Carl von Ossietzky Universitaet Oldenburg

July 17 - 18, 2009

Mathematical Models, Microbes & Evolutionary Diversification

Coordinators: Ivana Gudelj
Samantha Forde

Participants:
Ivana Gudelj
Samantha Forde
Hal Smith
Olin Silander
Rafael Pena-Miller
Konstantin Mischaikow
Justin Meyer
Christopher J. Marx
Tom Ferenci
Christina Burch
Martin Ackermann

Institutions:
Imperial College
University of California-Santa Cruz
Arizona State University
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology - Zurich
Imperial College
Rutgers University
Michigan State University
Harvard University
University of Sydney
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology - Zurich

September 9 - 11, 2009

Costs of Phenotypic Plasticity and Adaptation to Novel Environments

Coordinators: Courtney Murren
Carl Schlichting

Participants:
Courtney Murren
Carl Schlichting
Ulrich Steiner
Emilie Snell-Rood
Rick Relyea
David Pfennig
Heather Maughan
Joanna Masel
Heidi Maclean
Mary Heskell
Corey Handelsman
Cameron Ghalambor
Hilary Callahan

Institutions:
College of Charleston
University of Connecticut
Stanford University
University of Indiana - Bloomington
University of Pittsburgh
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
University of Toronto
University of Arizona
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Columbia University in the City of New York
Colorado State University
Colorado State University
Barnard College

October 2 - 6, 2009

An Integrative Evolutionary Approach to Examine Sexual Selection as a Mechanism of Speciation

Coordinators: Rebecca Safran
Albert Uy

Participants:
Carlos A. Botero
Rebecca Safran

Institutions:
NESCent
University of Colorado at Boulder

Albert Uy
Sander Van Doorn
Laurel Symes
Maria R. Servedio
Natalie Seddon
Dustin Rubenstein
Rafael Rodriguez
Patrik Nosil
Tamra Mendelson
Michael Kopp
Darren Irwin
Eileen Hebets
David Gray
Alicia Frame
Karen Carleton
Jenny Boughman

Syracuse University
University of Berne
Dartmouth College
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Oxford University
Columbia University
University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee
University of Colorado
University of Maryland - Baltimore County
University of Vienna
University of British Columbia
University of Nebraska
California State University - Northridge
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
University of Maryland - College Park
University of Wisconsin

October 8-12, 2009

Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology

Coordinators: Michal Kowalewski
Jennifer Stempien
Jonathan Payne

Participants:

Alison G. Boyer
Seth Finnegan
Richard Krause
Craig R. McClain
Philip Novack-Gottshall
Felisa A. Smith
Michal Kowalewski
Jennifer Stempien
Jonathan Payne

Institutions:

University of California-San Diego
Stanford University
Humboldt University
NESCent
University of West Georgia
University of New Mexico-Main Campus
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
University of Colorado at Boulder
Stanford University

October 12 - 15, 2009

Software for Bayesian Evolutionary Analysis by Sampling Trees

Coordinators: Alexei Drummond
Marc Suchard
Andrew Rambaut

Participants:

Alexei Drummond
Jeff Thorne
Marc Suchard
Beth Shapiro
Benjamin D. Redelings
Andrew Rambaut
Philippe Lemey
Kristin Lamm
Mark Holder
Joseph Heled
Aaron Darling
Peter Beerli

Institutions:

University of Auckland
North Carolina State University
University of California - Los Angeles
Pennsylvania State University
North Carolina State University
University of Edinburgh
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
North Carolina State University
University of Kansas Main Campus
University of Auckland
University of California-Davis (Davis,CA)
Florida State University

Alexander Alekseyenko
Erik Bloomquist

New York University
The Ohio State University

October 16 - 18, 2009

Evolution and Development of Polyphenisms: Pathways to Innovation and Diversification

Coordinators: Armin Moczek
David Pfennig

Participants:

Carl Schlichting
Fred Nijhout
Armin Moczek
Cris C. Ledon-Rettig
Susan Foster
Ian Dworkin
Tami Cruickshank
Ehab Abouheif
David Pfennig
Matt Wund
Mary Jane West-Eberhard
Sonia E. Sultan
Emilie Snell-Rood

Institutions:

University of Connecticut
Duke University
University of Indiana
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Clark University
Michigan State University
Indiana University
McGill University
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
The College of New Jersey
Smithsonian Institute
Wesleyan University
University of Indiana

October 24 - 28, 2009

Mechanistic Distribution Models: Energetics, Fitness, and Population Dynamics

Coordinators: Joshua Tewksbury
Robert Holt
Lauren Buckley
Michael Angilletta

Participants:

Mark Urban
Joshua Tewksbury
Kimberly Sheldon
Michael Sears
Leslie Rissler
Warren P Porter
Sean Menke
Joel Kingsolver
Timothy Keitt
Robert Holt
George Gilchrist
Lisa Crozier
Amanda Chunco
Lauren Buckley
Michael Angilletta
Amy Angert

Institutions:

University of Connecticut
University of Washington
University of Washington
Bryn Mawr College
University of Alabama
University of Wisconsin - Madison
North Carolina State University
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
University of Texas - Austin
University of Florida
National Science Foundation
NOAA Fisheries
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Indiana State University
Colorado State University

November 19 - 20, 2009

How Does Cognition Evolve?

Coordinators: Brian Hare
Charlie Nunn

Participants:

Institutions:

Brian Hare
Victoria Wobber
Hippo Jin Tan
Kara Schroepfer
Alexandra Rosati
Charlie Nunn
Evan MacLean
Lucia Jacobs
Esther Herrmann
Daniel Haun
Nathan Emery
Josep Call
Elizabeth Brannon
Michael Platt

Duke University
Harvard University
Duke University
Duke University
Duke University
Harvard University
Duke University
University of California - Berkeley
Max Planck Institute
Max Planck Institute
Queen Mary University of London
Max Planck Institute
Duke University
Duke University

November 23 - 24, 2009

The Plant EvoGenomics Working Group: Advancing Comparative Functional Genomics

Coordinators: Jim Leebens-Mack
Todd Vision

Participants:
Steve Cannon
Gordon Burleigh
John Bowers
Mike Barker
Cecile Ane
Jim Leebens-Mack
Gane Ka-Shu Wong
Tandy Warnow
Todd Vision
Shin-Han Shiu
Sheldon McKay
Dani Durand
Rob DeSalle
Claude dePamphilis
Eric Carpenter

Institutions:
Iowa State University
University of Florida
University of Georgia
University of British Columbia
University of Wisconsin
Pennsylvania State University-Main Campus
University of Alberta
University of Texas
University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Michigan State University
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
Carnegie Mellon University
American Museum of Natural History
Pennsylvania State University
University of Alberta

Short-term Visitors

January 9 - 16, 2009

Toward a General Theory of Biological Invasions

Participants:

Glenda M Wardle
Daniel Taub
Inderjit Singh
Gordon A Fox
Jessica Gurevitch

Institutions:

The University of Sydney
Southwestern University
University of Delhi
University of South Florida
SUNY at Stony Brook

February 16 - 20, 2009

Integrating fossil and molecular data in the study of diversification

Participants:

Luke Harmon
Gene Hunt
Michael Alfaro

Institutions:

University of Idaho
Smithsonian Institutions
University of California-Los Angeles

Informatics Courses

July 6 - 10, 2009

An Introduction to Meta-analysis in Ecology and Evolutionary Biology

Coordinators: Jessica Gurevitch
Marc J. Lajeunesse
Kerrie Mengersen

Participants:

Jessica Gurevitch
Marc J. Lajeunesse
Kerrie Mengersen
Peter Wragg
Susan Wiser
Victor Vidal-Martinez
Pamela Reynolds
Noelle Relles
Justin Reeves
Kattia Palacio
Isabel Miranda
Edwin Lebrija
Hilmar Lapp
Allen Hurlbert
Jennifer Howeth
Liza Holeski
Nyeema Harris
Elizabeth Harp
Ellen Gerton
Orou Gaoue
Kathryn Flinn
Javier delBarco-Trillo
Wayne Dawson
Federica Costantini
Scott Chamberlain
Dolaporn Auyeung

Institutions:

SUNY at Stony Brook
NESCent
Queensland University of Technology
University of Minnesota
Landcare Research
Centro de Investigacion y de Estudios Avanzados
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Virginia Institute of Marine Science
Kent State University
Universidad de Concepcion
Institute for Agricultural Plant Physiology & Ecology
Department of Plant Sciences, Tel Aviv University
NESCent
University of North Carolina
Yale University
University of Wisconsin
North Carolina State University
Colorado State University
Idaho State University
University of Miami
McGill University
Cornell University
Institute of Plant Sciences, University of Bern
University of Bologna
Rice University
Purdue University

July 9 - 19, 2009

Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course 2009 (Lisbon, Portugal)

Coordinators: William Piel
Hilmar Lapp
Pedro Fernandes

Participants:

William Piel
Hilmar Lapp
Pedro Fernandes
Ewa Wywiał
Filipa Sousa
Francois Serra
Rita Rasteiro
Malgorzata Palczewska
Maximilian Nesnidal
Kiwoong Nam

Institutions:

Yale University
NESCent
Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciencia
International Institute of Molecular and Cell Biology
Instituto de Tecnologia Quimica e Biologica
Centro de Investigacion Principe Felipe
IGC
Instituto de Tecnologia Quimica e Biologica
University of Hamburg
Uppsala University

Kessy Abarenkov
Hanna Guimaraes
Luis Goncalves
Miguel Fonseca
Anna Fiore-Donno
Ivo Chelo
Carlos Canchaya
Martina Bradic
Jason Blythe

University of Tartu
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
Universidade Nova de Lisboa
University of Porto
University of Oxford
IGC
University of Vigo
IGC and NYU
Wayne State University Medical School

July 16 - 19, 2009

2009 GMOD Summer School - Americas

Coordinators: David Clements

Participants:

Yunchen Gong
David Clements
Junjun Zhang
Bing Xue
Jesse Walsh
Aarti Venkat
Manuel Torres
Evan Staton
Daniel Standage
Chris Smith
Mitch Skinner
Arun Sethuraman
Adam Reitzel
Robert Reed
William Pulec
Abhishek Pratap
Joshua Orvis
Ankita Narang
Therese Mitros
Linda McMahan
Sheldon McKay
Weidong Mao
KuanLiang Liu
Ed Lee
Carson Holt
Curtis Hendrickson
Dong He
Vladimir Gapeyev
Eric Ganko
Joseph Franklin
Stephen Ficklin
Justin Elser
Newton de Vidal Medeiros
Scott Cain
Riyue Bao

Institutions:

University of Toronto
NESCent
Ontario Institute for Cancer Research
University of Missouri - Kansas City
Iowa State University
University of Illinois
University of Georgia
University of Georgia
Brigham Young University
North Carolina State University
University of California - Berkeley
Iowa State University
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institutions
University of California - Irvine
University of Wisconsin
Institute for Genome Sciences
Institute for Genome Sciences
Institute for Genomics & Integrative Biology
University of California - Berkeley
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
Virginia State University
Los Alamos National Laboratory
Berkeley National Laboratory
University of Utah
University of Alabama - Birmingham
California Technology
NESCent
Syngenta
Yale University
Clemson University
Oregon State University
Instituto Carlos Chagas
Ontario Institute for Cancer Research
Wayne State University

August 3 - 6, 2009

2009 GMOD Summer School – Europe (Oxford, UK)

Coordinators: David Clements

Participants:

Jun Zhao
Junjun Zhang
Xikun Wu
Emiel Ver Loren van Themaat
Giles Velarde
Wouter Van Gool
Emilie Tessier
Steve Taylor
Jan Strauss
Nina Stoletzki
Noel Smith
Miquel Ramia
Sheldon McKay
Simon McGowan
Siu-wai Leung
Jacob Lemieux
Ed Lee
Michel Jansen
Bernd Jagla
Robin Houston
Iam Holmes
Zong-Pei Han
Syed Haider
Cyprien Guerin
Antonio Frenandez-Guerra
Sven Dietz
Etienne de Villiers
Ines de Santiago
David Clements
Olympe Chazara
Tim Carver
Wilfrid Carre
Scott Cain
Baptiste Brault
Timothy Booth
Erick Antezana
Ambrose Andongabo
Paul-Michael Agapow

Institutions:

University of Oxford
Ontario Institute for Cancer Research
Institute for Animal Health
Max Planck Inst. for Plant Breeding Research
Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute
VIB Bioinformatics Facility
University of Rouen
University of Oxford
University of East Anglia
University of Sussex
Veterinary Laboratories Agency
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
University of Oxford
University of Edinburgh
Oxford University
Lawrence Berkeley National Lab
Top Institute Food & Nutrition
Institute Pasteur
Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute
University of California at Berkeley
University of Oxford
European Bioinformatics Institute
Inland Northwest Research Alliance
Centre d'Estudis Avanats de Blanes
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology
Keio University
Imperial College
NESCent
Inland Northwest Research Alliance
Sanger Institute
Inland Northwest Research Alliance
Ontario Institute for Cancer Research
Inland Northwest Research Alliance
Centre for Ecology and Hydrology
Bayer BioScience
Rothamsted Research
Institute for Animal Health

Informatics Working Groups

March 9 - 13, 2009

NESCent Database Interoperability Hackathon

Coordinators: Hilmar Lapp
Arlin Stoltzfus
Todd Vision
Rutger Vos

Participants:

Institutions:

Hilmar Lapp
Mark A. Jensen
Gregory E. Jordan
Matthew A. Kosnik
Sheldon McKay
Peter E. Midford
William Piel
Enrico Pontelli
Ryan Scherle
James P. Balhoff
Lucie Chan
Brandon Chisham
David Clements
Karen Cransten
Samuel N. Donnelly
Karla Gendler
Vivek Gopalan
Roger Hyam
Katja Seltmann
Arlin Stoltzfus
Jeet Sukumaran
Todd Vision
Rutger Vos
Matthew Yoder

Duke University
Fortinbras Research
EBI
Smithsonian Institutions
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
University of Kansas Main Campus
Yale University
New Mexico State University-Main Campus
Duke University
NESCent
San Diego Supercomputer Center
New Mexico State University-Main Campus
NESCent
University of Arizona
University of Pennsylvania
University of Arizona
National Institutes of Health
NHM London / RBG Edinburgh/ TDWG
Morphbank, HAO
California Air Resources Board
University of Kansas Main Campus
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
University of British Columbia
Ohio State University Agricultural Technical Inst

April 27 - 30, 2009

Evolutionary Ontologies Workshop

Coordinators: Monte Westerfield
Todd Vision
Paula Mabee

Participants:

Anne Maglia
Austin Mast
Peter E. Midford
Cyndy Parr
Greg Riccardi
Paul Sereno
Arlin Stoltzfus
Peter Vize
Monte Westerfield
Todd Vision
Paula Mabee
Judith A. Blake
Jonathan Coddington
Lindsay Cowell
Andy Deans
Betsy Dumont
Eva Huala
Hilmar Lapp
Suzi Lewis
John Lundberg

Institutions:

Missouri University of Science and Technology
Florida State University
University of Kansas
Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History
The Florida State University College of Information
University of Chicago
National Institute of Standards and Technology
University of Calgary
University of Oregon - Institute of Neuroscience
NESCent
University of South Dakota
The Jackson Lab
Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History
Duke University
North Carolina State University
University of Massachusetts Amherst
Carnegie Institutions for Science
NESCent
Berkeley Informatics and Ontology Project
Academy of Natural Sciences

May 21 - 22, 2009

Dryad Management Board Meeting

Coordinators: Peggy Schaeffer
Todd Vision

Participants:

Hilmar Lapp
Marcel Holyoak
Harold Heatwole
Jane Greenberg
Erica Fleishman
Peggy Schaeffer
Sarah Carrier
C. Scott Baker
John Allen
William Michener
Mohamed Noor
Allen Moore
Todd Vision
Rod Page
Ryan Scherle
Kathleen K Smith
Michelle Tseng
Marcy Uyenoyama
Tim Vines
Peter J Wagner
Hollie White
Michael Whitlock
Derek Wildman

Institutions:

NESCent
University of California
North Carolina State University
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
NCEAS
NESCent
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Oregon State University
University of Southampton
University of New Mexico
Duke University
University of Exeter
NESCent
University of Glasgow
NESCent
Duke University
University of British Columbia
Duke University
University of British Columbia
Smithsonian Institutions
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
University of British Columbia
Wayne State University

EOG Courses

June 29 - 1, 2009

Evolution 2009: A Workshop for Educators

Coordinators: Kristin Jenkins
Jory P. Weintraub
Alex Glass
Jenny Tung

Participants:

Kristin Jenkins
Jory P Weintraub
Linda Woody
Lisa Siegeman
Jessica Sandel
Joshua Roberts
Carolyn Primeaux
Lorie Poff
Jessalyn Pearson
Elizabeth Mayo
Jordan Kevin
Mika Hunter
Tara Culbertson
Sarah Kaneko
Brian M. Wiegmann
Michaela Creech
Elizabeth Buck (Bunnie) Bradley
Erin Bode
Alex Glass
Kathryn Perez
Robin A. Smith
Jenny Tung

Institutions:

NESCent
NESCent
Reidsville High School
Millbrook High School
Jordan-Matthews High School
Northern High School
Orange High School
Grimsley High School
Hillside High School
Orange High School
Green Hope High School
Riverside High School
Northwest High school
C.E. Jordan High School
Duke University
Dudley High School
Havelock High School
East Columbus High School
Duke University
University of Wisconsin-La Crosse
NESCent
Duke University

EOG Working Groups

May 8 - 9, 2009

Evolution across the curriculum

Coordinators: Judy Scotchmoor
Gordon Uno

Participants:

Judy Scotchmoor
Gordon Uno
Jory P. Weintraub
Jay B. Labov
Kristin Jenkins
Paul Beardsley

Institutions:

University of California-Berkeley
University of Oklahoma Norman Campus
NESCent
National Academy of Sciences
NESCent
Biological Science Curriculum Study

September 24 - 26, 2009

Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education EOG TREE

Coordinators: Sam Donovan

Participants:

Institutions:

Sam Donovan
Paul Beardsley
Kristy Havlerson
Jon Herron
Kristin Jenkins
Erin Naegle
James J. Smith
Jory P. Weintraub
Aimee Young
Stacey D. Smith

University of Pittsburgh-Main Campus
Biological Sciences Curriculum Study
University of Southern Mississippi
University of Washington
NESCent
Grand Valley State University
Michigan State University
NESCent
University of Massachusetts - Boston
Duke University

October 6 - 7, 2009

Synthesis Center Education and Outreach

Coordinators: Kristin Jenkins

Participants:

Kristin Jenkins
Martha Narro
Audrey Aronowsky
Tracy Barbaro
Margaret Connors
Jennifer Walton
Susan Musante
Lisa Howells
Jacki Reeves-Pepin
Robin A. Smith
Judy Verbeke
Wendy Graham
Jory P. Weintraub
Brian M. Wiegmann

Institutions:

NESCent
iPlant Collaborative
BioSync
EOL
NCEAS
NIMBioS
American Institute of Biological Sciences
iPlant Collaborative
NABT
National Evolutionary Synthesis Center
NSF
NEON
NESCent
North Carolina State University

Advisory Board Meetings

February 5 - 6, 2009

Science Advisory Board

Participants:

Stan Blum
Troy Day
Fred Gould
Catherine Graham
Elizabeth Hadly
Joe Niegel
Maria Orive
Bill Piel
Bruce Rannala
Todd Strelman
Paul Turner
Cheryl Wilga

Institutions:

California Academy of Sciences
Queens University
North Carolina State University
SUNY at Stony Brook
Stanford University
University of Louisiana at Lafayette
University of Kansas
Yale University
University of California at Davis
Georgia Tech University
Yale University
University of Rhode Island

September 10 - 11, 2009

NESCent Advisory Board

Participants:

Stan Blum
Cheryl Wilga
Marta L. Wayne
Maureen Stanton
William Piel
Allen Rodrigo
Rod Page
Maria Orive
Anne Maglia
Ray Huey
Joseph L. Graves Jr
Bruce Rannala
Joel Kingsolver
Sarah Tishkoff
Tony Zera

Institutions:

California Academy of Sciences
University of Rhode Island
University of Florida
University of California, Davis
Yale University
University of Auckland
University of Glasgow
University of Kansas
Missouri University of Science and Technology
University of Washington
North Carolina A&T University
University of California, Davis
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
University of Pennsylvania
The University of Nebraska, Lincoln

Hosted Meetings

May 7 - 8, 2009

IPlant Phylogeny GC Team Meeting (IPTOL)

Coordinators: Rich Jorgenson
Mike Sanderson

Participants:

Patrick Herendeen
Michael Sanderson
Michael Donoghue
Pam Soltis
Doug Soltis
Val Tannen
Todd Vision
Alexis Stamatakis
Dan Stanzione
Rich Jorgensen
Steve Goff
Rick Blevins
Sheldon McKay
Matt Vaughn
Karla Gendler
Damian Gessler
Brenton Elmore

Institutions:

Chicago Botanic Garden
University of Arizona
Yale University
University of Florida
University of Florida
University of Pennsylvania
University of North Carolina/NECent
Technical University of Munich
iPlant
iPlant
iPlant
iPlant
iPlant
iPlant
iPlant
iPlant
iPlant

September 9 - 11, 2009

Future Directions in Systematics

Coordinators: Patrick Herendeen
Brian M. Wiegmann

Participants:

Patrick Herendeen
Maureen Kearney
Mary Liz Jameson
Amy Heilman
James Hanken
Vicki Funk
Jeff Doyle
Rafael de Sa
Bryan Danforth
Tim Collins
James Clark
Robb Brumfield
David Baum
Brian M. Wiegmann
David L. Swofford
Pam Soltis
Scott Snyder
Nancy Simmons
Petra Sierwald
Nathan Sheffield
Scott Santos
Fabian Michelangeli

Institutions:

Chicago Botanic Garden
National Science Foundation
Wichita State University
Duke University
Harvard University
Smithsonian Institutions
Cornell University
National Science Foundation
Cornell University
National Science Foundation
George Washington University
Louisiana State University
University of Wisconsin
North Carolina State University
Duke University
University of Florida
National Science Foundation
American Museum
Field Museum
Duke University
Auburn University
New York Botanical Garden

Lucinda McDade
Irby Lovette
Bruce Lieberman
Jim Leebens-Mack
Robert Thacker
Michelle Trautwein
Rytas Vilgalys

Rancho Santa Ana Botanic Garden
Cornell University
University of Kansas
University of Georgia
University of Alabama
North Carolina State University
Duke University

October 1 - 2, 2009

Evolution and Global Change in the Oceans Workshop

Coordinators: Gretchen Hofmann

Participants:

Michael Behrenfeld
Ginger Armbrust
Gretchen Hofmann
Robin Waples
Steve Palumbi
Alison Murray
Amy Moran
Carol Lee
David Kirchman
Joel Kingsolver
Dave Hutchins
Brian Helmuth
Sinead Collins

Institutions:

Oregon State University
University of Washington
University of California-Santa Barbara
National Marine Fisheries Service
Stanford University
University of Nevada-Reno
Clemson University
University of Wisconsin
University of Delaware
University of North Carolina
University of Southern California
University of South Carolina
University of Edinburgh

Appendix 7: Student Interns at NESCent in Year 5

Name	Institution	Mentor	Project
Undergraduate Students			
Alex Ahearn	Duke University	Wasila Dahdul	Phenoscape Curation
Alexandra Balaban	Duke University	Ganesh Ganapathy	New Methods and Pattern Identification in Biogeography
Rebecca Dyer	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	Danielle Wilson	Development of NESCent statistical data for NSF reporting
Tiffany Gillis	Duke University	Danielle Wilson	Development of NESCent statistical data for NSF reporting
Taylor Gullett	Duke University	Craig McClain	The Evolution of Body Size in Deep-Sea Bivalves
Justine Jackson-Ricketts	Duke University	Craig McClain	Morphological Disparity of Gastropods Through the Phanerozoic
Rosie Kilgore	Duke University	Ryan Scherle	Dryad Curation
Jonathan Lee	Duke University	Wasila Dahdul	Phenoscape Curation
Vanessa Mallol	Duke University	Eric Schuettpelz	A Phylogenetic Approach to Understanding the Evolution of the Earth's Biomes
Carla Perez	Duke University	Wasila Dahdul	Phenoscape Curation
Courtney Peterson	Duke University	Danielle Wilson	Development of NESCent statistical data for NSF reporting

Graduate Students			
Amol Bapat	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	Jane Greenberg	Development of the Dryad Repository Interface and System Architecture
Sarah Carrier	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	Jane Greenberg	Qualitative Study of NESCent Publications
Sarah Diamond	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	Joel Kingsolver	Development of NESCent Science and Synthesis Products Relating to Awards
Michael Graves	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	Jane Greenberg	Development of “Handshaking” Between Dryad and Other Data Repositories
Mtakai Ngara	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Kenya	Todd Vision	Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies
Sandrine Tercerie	Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, France	Todd Vision	Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies
Holly White	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	Jane Greenberg	Development of Dryad-Data Attitudes and Behavior Survey

Appendix 8a: Demographics for postdoctoral fellows for year 5 (12/1/08-11/30/09) and years 1-5 (12/1/04-11/30/09). Table includes information on gender, residency, ethnicity, race, and citizenship for all applicants, those applicants approved for funding that accepted, applicants approved who did not accept, and those not selected for funding. Bold values indicate column and row totals.

	Year 5				Years 1-5			
	postdoc Applicants	approved-accepted	approved-declined	not approved	postdoc Applicants	approved-accepted	approved-declined	not approved
Gender								
Did Not Provide	0	0	0	0	14	1	2	11
Female	6	1	1	4	40	9	6	25
Male	22	5	4	13	66	17	6	43
Total	28	6	5	17	120	27	14	79
Residency								
Non U.S.	4	0	1	3	21	1	2	18
U.S.	24	6	4	14	99	26	12	61
Total	28	6	5	17	120	27	14	79
Ethnicity								
Did Not Provide	0	0	0	0	19	4	2	13
Do not wish to provide	1	0	0	1	7	0	2	5
Hispanic or Latino	1	1	0	0	3	2	0	1
Not Hispanic or Latino	26	5	5	16	91	21	10	60
Total	28	6	5	17	120	27	14	79
Race								
Did Not Provide	0	0	0	0	19	4	2	13
Do not wish to provide	1	0	0	1	7	0	2	5
Hispanic or Latino	1	1	0	0	3	2	0	1
Not Hispanic or Latino	26	5	5	16	91	21	10	60
Total	28	6	5	17	120	27	14	79
Citizenship								
Did Not Provide	0	0	0	0	16	1	2	13
Non-US Citizen	8	2	0	6	15	6	0	9
Other non-U.S. Citizen	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	18
Permanent Resident	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
US Citizen	19	4	5	10	70	20	12	38
Total	28	6	5	17	120	27	14	79

Appendix 8b: Demographics for scholars for year 5 (12/1/08-11/30/09) and years 1-5 (12/1/04-11/30/09). Table includes information on gender, residency, ethnicity, race, and citizenship for all applicants, those applicants approved for funding that accepted, applicants approved who did not accept, and those not selected for funding. Bold values indicate column and row totals.

	Year 5				Years 1-5			
	approved-accepted	approved-declined	not approved	Total	approved-accepted	approved-declined	not approved	Total
Long-term Sabbatical								
Gender								
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	2	0	4	6
Female	0	1	0	1	2	1	0	3
Male	3	0	4	7	14	2	9	25
Total	3	1	4	8	18	3	13	34
Residency								
Non U.S.	0	0	1	1	2	0	3	4
U.S.	3	1	3	7	16	3	10	30
Total	3	1	4	8	18	3	13	34
Ethnicity								
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	7	0	7	14
Do not wish to provide	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Not Hispanic or Latino	3	1	4	8	11	3	6	20
Total	3	1	4	8	18	3	13	34
Race								
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	6	1	8	15
Asian	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Do not wish to provide	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
White	3	1	4	8	12	2	5	19
Total	3	1	4	8	18	3	13	34
Citizenship								
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	5	0	7	13
Non-US Citizen	0	0	1	1	2	0	2	3
Permanent Resident	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
US Citizen	3	1	3	7	11	3	4	18
Total	3	1	4	8	18	3	13	34

Appendix 8b cont.: Applicant Data for Scholars: gender, residency (based on home institution), ethnicity, race, and citizenship

	Year 5				Years 1-5			
	approved-accepted	approved-declined	not approved	Total	approved-accepted	approved-declined	not approved	Total
Short-term Visitor								
Gender								
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	4	0	2	6
Female	0	0	0	0	13	0	1	14
Male	5	0	0	5	36	0	3	39
Total	5	0	0	5	53	0	6	59
Residency								
Non U.S.	3	0	0	3	23	0	2	25
U.S.	2	0	0	2	30	0	4	34
Total	5	0	0	5	53	0	6	59
Ethnicity								
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	7	0	3	10
Do not wish to provide	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	8
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	3
Not Hispanic or Latino	5	0	0	5	35	0	3	38
Total	5	0	0	5	53	0	6	59
Race								
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	10	0	4	14
Asian	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	5
Do not wish to provide	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	4
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	3
White	5	0	0	5	32	0	1	33
Total	5	0	0	5	53	0	6	59
Citizenship								
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	7	0	2	9
Non-US Citizen	3	0	0	3	13	0	0	13
Permanent Resident	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2
US Citizen	2	0	0	2	32	0	3	35
Total	5	0	0	5	53	0	6	59

Appendix 8c: Demographics of applicants for catalysis and working groups for year 5 (12/1/08-11/30/09) and years 1-5 (12/1/04-11/30/09). Table includes information on gender, residency, ethnicity, race, and citizenship for all applicants, those applicants approved for funding that accepted, and those not selected for funding. No cases occur where applicants were approved and did not accept. Bold values indicate column and row totals.

	Year 5			Years 1-5		
	approved-accepted	not approved	Total	approved-accepted	not approved	Total
Catalysis Meetings						
Gender						
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	5	5
Female	2	4	6	10	5	15
Male	6	7	13	23	28	51
Total	8	11	19	33	38	71
Residency						
Do not wish to provide	4	7	11	10	10	20
Non U.S.	1	1	2	5	3	8
U.S.	3	3	6	18	25	43
Total	8	11	19	33	38	71
Ethnicity						
Not Provided	0	0	0	9	6	15
Do not wish to provide	4	5	9	6	8	14
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	1	1	2
Not Hispanic or Latino	4	6	10	17	23	40
Total	8	11	19	33	38	71
Race						
Not Provided	0	0	0	11	16	27
Asian	0	0	0	0	0	0
Black or African American	0	0	0	0	0	0
Do not wish to provide	4	5	9	6	5	11
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	1	1	2
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	0	0	0	0	2	2
White	4	6	10	15	14	29
Total	8	11	19	33	38	71
Citizenship						
Not Provided	0	0	0	1	5	6
Do not wish to provide	3	2	5	4	2	6
Non-US Citizen	1	0	1	4	2	6
Other non-U.S. Citizen	0	0	0	0	1	1
Permanent Resident	0	0	0	1	0	1
US Citizen	4	9	13	23	28	51
Total	8	11	19	33	38	71

Appendix 8c cont.: Applicant Data for Group PI's: gender, residency (based on home institution), ethnicity, race, and citizenship

	Year 5			Years 1-5		
	approved-accepted	not approved	Total	approved-accepted	not approved	Total
Working Groups						
Gender						
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	10	10
Female	6	3	9	21	15	36
Male	12	21	33	38	44	82
Total	18	24	42	59	69	128
Residency						
Do not wish to provide	4	4	8	8	5	13
Non U.S.	3	4	7	6	11	17
U.S.	11	16	27	45	53	98
Total	18	24	42	59	69	128
Ethnicity						
Not Provided	0	0	0	4	11	15
Do not wish to provide	4	0	4	6	3	9
Hispanic or Latino	0	1	1	0	1	1
Not Hispanic or Latino	14	23	37	49	54	103
Total	18	24	42	59	69	128
Race						
Not Provided	0	0	0	6	20	26
Asian	1	2	3	1	3	4
Black or African American	0	0	0	1	0	1
Do not wish to provide	4	0	4	5	0	5
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	0	0	0
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	0	0	0	0	0	0
White	13	22	35	46	46	92
Total	18	24	42	59	69	128
Citizenship						
Not Provided	0	0	0	1	10	11
Do not wish to provide	0	0	0	0	2	2
Non-US Citizen	6	2	7	8	6	14
Other non-U.S. Citizen	0	0	0	0	0	0
Permanent Resident	0	2	2	1	3	4
US Citizen	12	20	33	49	48	97
Total	18	24	42	59	69	128

Appendix 8d: Summary demographics for awarded scholars and group principal investigators for year 5 (12/1/08-11/30/09) and years 1-5 (12/1/04-11/30/09). Table includes information on gender, residency, ethnicity, race, and citizenship for all applicants, those applicants approved for funding that accepted, applicants approved but did not accept, and those not selected for funding. Bold values indicate column and row totals.

	Catalysis Meetings	Working Groups	Long-term Sabbaticals	Postdoctoral Fellows	Short-Term Visitor
Year 5					
Gender					
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	0
Female	2	6	0	1	0
Male	6	12	3	5	5
Total	8	18	3	6	5
Residency					
Do not wish to provide	4	4	0	0	0
Non U.S.	1	3	0	0	3
U.S.	3	11	3	6	2
Total	8	18	3	6	5
Ethnicity					
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	0
Do not wish to provide	4	4	0	0	0
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	1	0
Not Hispanic or Latino	4	14	3	5	5
Total	8	18	3	6	5
Race					
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	0
Asian	0	1	0	0	0
Black or African American	0	0	0	0	0
Do not wish to provide	4	4	0	0	0
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	1	0
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	0	0	0	0	0
White	4	13	3	5	5
Total	8	18	3	6	5
Citizenship					
Not Provided	0	0	0	0	0
Do not wish to provide	3	0	0	0	0
Non-US Citizen	1	6	0	2	3
Other non-U.S. Citizen	0	0	0	0	0
Permanent Resident	0	0	0	0	0
US Citizen	4	12	3	4	2
Total	8	18	3	6	5

Appendix 8d cont.: Award Data for Scholars and Group PI's: gender, residency (based on home institution), ethnicity, race, and citizenship

	Catalysis Meetings	Working Groups	Long-term Sabbaticals	Postdoctoral Fellows	Short-Term Visitor
Years 1-5					
Gender					
Not Provided	0	0	2	1	4
Female	10	21	2	9	13
Male	23	38	14	17	36
Total	33	59	18	27	53
Residency					
Do not wish to provide	10	8	0	0	0
Non U.S.	5	6	2	1	23
U.S.	18	45	16	26	30
Total	33	59	18	27	53
Ethnicity					
Not Provided	9	4	7	4	7
Do not wish to provide	6	6	0	0	8
Hispanic or Latino	1	0	0	2	3
Not Hispanic or Latino	17	49	11	21	35
Total	33	59	18	27	53
Race					
Not Provided	11	6	6	4	10
Asian	0	1	0	0	4
Black or African American	0	1	0	0	0
Do not wish to provide	6	5	0	0	4
Hispanic or Latino	1	0	0	2	3
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	0	0	0	0	0
White	15	46	12	21	33
Total	33	59	18	27	53
Citizenship					
Not Provided	1	1	5	1	7
Do not wish to provide	4	0	0	0	0
Non-US Citizen	4	8	2	6	13
Other non-U.S. Citizen	0	0	0	0	0
Permanent Resident	1	1	0	0	1
US Citizen	23	49	11	20	32
Total	33	59	18	27	53

Appendix 8e: Demographics for participants in meetings and courses in Year 5 (12/1/09-11/30/09). Data is calculated by unique visits to NESCent. Table includes information on gender, residency, ethnicity, race, and citizenship. Bold values indicate column and row totals. Table does not include seminar speakers or interns.

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group Meeting	EOG Working Group Meeting	Informatics Working Group Meeting	Informatics Course	EOG Course	Science Advisory Board Meetings	Hosted Meeting	Total
Gender									
Not Provided	20	8	7	4	82	3	0	15	139
Do not wish to provide	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	4
Female	21	89	18	23	14	14	6	10	195
Male	63	152	26	60	23	5	9	32	370
Total	105	251	51	88	119	22	15	57	708
Residency									
Non U.S.	49	69	12	19	95	3	4	17	268
U.S.	56	182	39	69	24	19	11	40	440
Total	105	251	51	88	119	22	15	57	708
Ethnicity									
Not Provided	20	15	9	5	86	3	0	21	159
Do not wish to provide	15	11	0	5	0	0	0	0	31
Hispanic or Latino	4	13	2	2	6	1	1	4	33
Not Hispanic or Latino	66	212	40	76	27	18	14	32	485
Total	105	251	51	88	119	22	15	57	708
Race									
Not Provided	20	16	9	5	86	3	0	21	160
American Indian or Alaska Native	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Asian	6	3	1	5	2	2	1	0	20
Black or African American	1	2	0	0	2	2	1	0	8
Do not wish to provide	14	19	1	6	1	0	0	1	42
Hispanic or Latino	2	11	1	1	3	1	1	2	22
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
White	62	200	39	71	24	14	11	33	454
Total	105	251	51	88	119	22	15	57	708
Citizenship									
Not Provided	20	10	8	4	86	3	0	18	149
Do not wish to provide	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
Non-US Citizen	30	45	2	13	11	1	2	2	106
Permanent Resident	4	15	1	5	4	0	1	3	33
US Citizen	47	179	40	66	18	18	12	34	414
Total	105	251	51	88	119	22	15	57	708

Appendix 8f: Home institution type of participants in NESCent activities in year 5 by unique visits. Activities include catalysis meeting, working group meetings, courses, board meetings, and hosted meetings. The difference in totals between 8f and 8g reflects a participant in Year 5 from an “other organization” with multiple offices across the globe.

Institution Type	Count
Associate granting Universities	3
Baccalaureate Colleges	8
K-12 Schools	13
Doctorate-granting Universities	429
Government Organizations	18
International Botanical Gardens	1
International Museums	2
International Research Institutes	39
International Universities	82
Master's Colleges and Universities	15
Medical School	2
Other Organizations	13
Research Centers	70
Special Focus Institutions	5
US Botanical Gardens	4
US Medical Institutes	4
US Museums	17
US Research Institutes	38
US University	3
Total Institutions	766

Appendix 8g: Location of institutions by country of participants by unique visit. Table and maps give counts for years 1-5 (12/1/04-11/30/09) and year 5 separately (12/1/08-11/30/09). Includes seminar speakers and interns.

Country	Years 1-5	Year 5
Argentina	8	1
Australia	21	7
Austria	3	1
Bangladesh	1	0
Belgium	4	3
Bolivia	1	1
Brazil	5	1
Canada	116	31
Chile	14	1
China	1	1
Colombia	2	1
Czech Republic	3	0
Denmark	11	1
Dominican Republic	1	0
Estonia	1	1
Ethiopia	1	1
Finland	1	0
France	19	7
Germany	28	9
India	2	2
Ireland	2	1
Israel	2	2
Italy	2	1
Jamaica	1	0
Japan	7	0
Kyrgyzstan	1	1
Mexico	5	3
Netherlands	9	3
New Zealand	11	4
Norway	1	0
Panama	4	0
Peru	1	1
Poland	1	1
Portugal	7	6
Singapore	1	0
South Africa	1	1
Spain	13	6
Sweden	10	3
Switzerland	14	8
United Kingdom	116	47
United States	2583	608
Total	3035	765

NESCent Participants by Countries in Year 5

NESCent Participants by Countries in Year 1-5

Appendix 8g: Location of institutions by state in the U.S. of funded participants by unique visit. Table and maps give counts for years 1-5 (12/1/04-11/30/09) and year 5 separately (12/1/04-11/30/09). Includes seminar speakers and interns.

State	Years 1-5	Year 5
Alaska	2	1
Alabama	7	4
Arizona	43	12
California	255	70
Colorado	36	15
Connecticut	76	21
District of Columbia	75	17
Delaware	3	1
Florida	57	13
Georgia	41	8
Hawaii	9	0
Iowa	21	8
Idaho	11	6
Illinois	65	15
Indiana	27	12
Kansas	28	11
Kentucky	3	0
Louisiana	18	3
Massachusetts	100	30
Maryland	44	12
Maine	3	1
Michigan	53	11
Minnesota	23	4
Missouri	34	7
Mississippi	2	1
Montana	8	0
North Carolina	850	164
Nebraska	9	3
New Hampshire	8	1
New Jersey	23	5
New Mexico	22	9
Nevada	2	1
New York	129	43
Ohio	27	7
Oklahoma	4	1
Oregon	29	7
Pennsylvania	65	17
Puerto Rico	5	0
Rhode Island	11	8
South Carolina	15	4
South Dakota	13	2
Tennessee	10	4
Texas	33	5

Utah	22	3
Virginia	46	15
Vermont	4	2
Washington	178	12
Wisconsin	31	12
West Virginia	1	0
Wyoming	2	0
Total	2583	608

NESCent Participants in Year 5

NESCent Participants in Year 1-5

Appendix 9a: NESCent website traffic and statistics (Jan. 1, 2006-Sep. 29, 2009). Top figure shows the number of weekly page views (blue) and average time spent by a user (orange). Note that both page views and average visitor time have increased since March 1, 2009 (red shaded box). Statistics do not include traffic from NESCent affiliated computers.

Site Usage Metrics for Jan. 1, 2006-Sep. 29, 2009

Origination of Website Visitors, Direct traffic denotes visitors typing url or through a browser bookmark, Search Engines by searching for NESCent in Google or similar site, Referring Sites are visitors who arrive at the site by a link from another website

Total Visitors: 145,705
 New Visitors: 73,082 (50.16%)
 Returning Visitors: 72,623 (49.84%)

Visitor Locations

North Carolina: 55,511
 USA (non-North Carolina): 58,996
 International: 31,198

Most Frequently Visited Pages

1. Education and Outreach Home
2. Science and Synthesis Home
3. About NESCent
4. Informatics Home
5. Awards Page

Appendix 9b: Press Coverage of NESCent Science and Activities for Year 5

General

- Bates, K. 2009. Putting it all together again: Frontier of biology assembles data, looks for patterns. Duke Research Magazine. <http://research.duke.edu/putting-it-all-together-again/index.html>

Working Groups

Measuring evolutionary change in modern human populations using cohort data

PI(s): Diddahally Govindaraju (Boston University)

Andrew Clark (Cornell University)

Trudy Mackay (North Carolina State University at Raleigh)

Stephen Stearns (Yale University)

- Johnson, C. 2009. People are still evolving, heart study numbers say. The Boston Globe. http://www.boston.com/business/healthcare/articles/2009/10/26/evolution_continues_framingham_heart_study_says/
- Harrell, E. 2009. Darwin Lives! Modern Humans Are Still Evolving. TIME. <http://www.time.com/time/health/article/0,8599,1931757,00.html>
- Torrice, M. 2009. We're Still Evolving--And We May Be Shrinking. Science Magazine. <http://sciencenow.sciencemag.org/cgi/content/full/2009/1022/1>
- Palca, J. Natural selection works on humans too. NPR's Science Friday. <http://www.npr.org/templates/story/story.php?storyId=114081469&ft=1&f=1007>
- Paddock, C. 2009. Humans Are Still Evolving, Study Shows. Medical News Today. <http://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/167915.php>
- Unknown. 2009. Women to be shorter, more fertile in future. Deccan Chronicle. <http://www.deccanchronicle.com/health/women-be-shorter-more-fertile-future-361>
- 2009. Humans continuing to evolve. The Colorado Springs Gazette. <http://www.gazette.com/articles/continuing-64359-traits-humans.html>
- Holmes, B. 2009. Meet future woman: shorter, plumper, more fertile. New Scientist. <http://www.newscientist.com/article/dn17997-meet-future-woman-shorter-plumper-more-fertile.html?DCMP=OTC-rss&nsref=online-news>

- Chivers, T. 2009. Women evolving to be shorter and heavier, says research. Telegraph. <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/science/evolution/6386193/Women-evolving-to-be-shorter-and-heavier-says-research.html>

Visiting Scholars

Wasila Dahdul:

- Fields, H. 2009. ScienceNOW Daily News: How the Piranha Got Its Teeth. Science. <http://sciencenow.sciencemag.org/cgi/content/full/2009/629/1>
- Minard, A. 2009. Yard-long "Megapiranha" Fossil Found. National Geographic News. <http://news.nationalgeographic.com/news/2009/06/photogalleries/giant-piranha-pictures-evolution/>
- 2009. Huge 'Megapiranha' fossil found in South America. Fox News. <http://www.foxnews.com/story/0,2933,529195,00.html>
- 2009. Toothy 3-foot Piranha Fossil Found. US News and World Report. <http://www.usnews.com/articles/science/plants-animals/2009/06/25/toothy-3-foot-piranha-fossil-found.html>
- 2009. Toothy 3-foot piranha fossil found: Remains bridge evolutionary gap between flesh eaters and plant eaters. MSNBC News. http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/31553901/ns/technology_and_science-science/
- Flam, Faye. 2009. Unearthing the megapiranha. Philadelphia Inquirer. http://www.philly.com/inquirer/magazine/20090706_Unearthing_the_megapiranha.html

Postdoctoral Fellows

Brian O'Meara:

- Suter, S. (2009). Editor's choice: Unable to diversify. Science 325(5936): 12. <http://www.scienceonline.org/content/vol325/issue5936/twil.dtl#325/5936/12-a>

Stephen Smith:

- Zimmer, C. (2009). Crunching the data for the tree of life. New York Times. New York, NY. <http://www.nytimes.com/2009/02/10/science/10tree.html>.
- Feb. 13, 2009. The tree of life grows denser, FEATURED ARTICLE, BMC Evol Biol.

- Heger, M. (2009). Climate change may be especially tough on trees. USA Today. <http://blogs.usatoday.com/sciencefair/2009/09/climate-change-may-be-especially-tough-on-trees.html>

Brian Sidlauskas:

- 2009. First land creatures had wild appearances. Fox News. <http://www.foxnews.com/story/0,2933,530674,00.html>

Eric Schuettpeiz:

- Bates, K. 2009. Ferns took to the trees and thrived. Duke University Office of News and Communications. <http://www.dukenews.duke.edu/2009/07/fernlife.html>.
- 2009. ScienceShots: Fern frenzy. Science Magazine. <http://sciencenow.sciencemag.org/science-shots/index.dtl?page=072009>
- Unknown. 2009. Ancient ferns bum a ride off giant trees. Futurity. <http://futuraity.org/earth-environment/ancient-ferns-bum-a-ride-from-giant-trees/>

Carlos Botero:

- 2009. Hard times make birds better singers. Australian Broadcasting Corporation. ABC Science. <http://www.abc.net.au/science/articles/2009/05/22/2578097.htm>
- Kessler, M. 2009. Mockingbirds: the tougher the weather, the better they sing. USA Today. <http://blogs.usatoday.com/sciencefair/2009/05/mockingbirds-the-tougher-the-weather-the-better-they-sing.html>
- Gill, V. 2009. Climate link to mockingbird songs. BBC News. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/science/nature/8062420.stm>. (This same story also ran in the Herald de Paris: <http://www.heralddeparis.com/climate-link-to-mockingbird-songs/36495>)
- Millius, S. 2009. For some birds, chancy climates mean better singers. Science News 175(13): 8. http://www.sciencenews.org/view/generic/id/44023/title/For_some_birds%2C_chancy_climates_mean_better_singers
- Alleyne, R. 2009. Birds are better at singing in the rain – and the cold. Daily Telegraph, UK. <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/earth/wildlife/5362862/Birds-are-better-at-singing-in-the-rain---and-the-cold.html>

- 2009. Animal behaviour: Singing in the rain. Nature Research Highlights 459: 487.
<http://www.nature.com/nature/journal/v459/n7246/full/459487b.html>
- Cane, A. 2009. Bird song linked to survival. Financial Times.
http://www.ft.com/cms/s/0/f4988c9c-4669-11de-803f-00144feabdc0.html?nclick_check=1
- Holden, C. 2009. Brainy birds get more chicks. Science Magazine.
<http://sciencenow.sciencemag.org/cgi/content/full/2009/821/1>
- Hirson, B. 2009. Science Update Radio Interview (AAAS). Climate-enhanced bird songs.
<http://www.scienceupdate.com/show.php?date=20090615>
- Conroy, M. 2009. How geeks get girls. Wired Magazine.
<http://www.wired.co.uk/news/archive/2009-08/20/how-geeks-get-girls.aspx>
- Smith, R.A. 2009. Mockingbirds in fickle climes sing fancier tunes. Duke University Office of News and Communications.
<http://www.dukenews.duke.edu/2009/05/mockingbird1.html>
- Gill, V. 2009. Songbirds sing cross-species duet. BBC News.
<http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/science/nature/8246424.stm>.
- Callaway, E. 2009. Why geeks get the girls. New Scientist.
<http://www.newscientist.com/article/dn17640-why-geeks-get-the-girls.html>.
- Holden, C. 2009. It's fit to be smart. Science Magazine.
<http://www.sciencemag.org/cgi/reprint/325/5944/1053-d.pdf>

Appendix 9c: NESCent Seminar Series for Year 5

Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
9-Jan-09	Ganesh Ganapathy	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	How to Calculate Species-Split Times and Ancestral Population Sizes Using Genomic Alignments
23-Jan-09	Brian O'Meara	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	What To Do In Year Three of Your NESCent Postdoc
30-Jan-09	Mike Antolin	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Colorado State University, Department of Biology	Postdoctoral Professional Development Activity: Talking to the Public About Evolution and Intelligent Design
6-Feb-09	Carlos Botero	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	The Evolution of Personality in Communication Strategies
13-Feb-09	Paula Spaeth	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	Practice Job Talk for Northland College Interview
20-Feb-09	Rutger Vos	NESCent Working Group Leader, University of British Columbia, Department of Zoology	Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis
27-Feb-09	Jonathon Cummings	Duke University, Fuqua School of Business	Organization Science of Science
13-Mar-09	Arlin Stoltzfus	NESCent Working Group Leader, Center for Advanced Research in Biotechnology	Evolutionary Informatics Working Group Report
27-Mar-09	Jeff Nekola	University of New Mexico	Evolutionary Pattern and Process in the <i>Vertigo gouldii</i> Group of Minute North American Land Snails

Appendix 9c: NESCent Seminar Series for Year 5

17-Apr-09	Nicholas Gessler	Duke University, Information Science and Information Studies Program	Artificial Life, Culture & Evolution – What We Gain, Lose, and What Stays the Same...
24-Apr-09	George Gilchrist	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, College of William and Mary, Department of Biology	Postdoctoral Professional Development Activity: How To Get Your NSF Grant Proposal Funded
1-May-09	Mark Batzer	Louisiana State University, Department of Biological Sciences	Mobile Elements and Genomic Variation
8-May-09	Sheldon McKay and Mike Sanderson	Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory (McKay) and University of Arizona (Sanderson)	Introduction and Q&A to the iPlant Tree of Life Project
15-May-09	Brian Sidlauskas	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	Fishheads, Phylomorphospaces and Unexpected Syntheses: Highlights from a Postdoc at NESCent
22-May-09	Bill Michener	e-Science Initiatives for University Libraries at the University of New Mexico, New Mexico EPSCoR State Program; LTER Network Office	DataONE: A Virtual Data Center for Enabling Data- Intensive Biological and Environmental Research
29-May-09	Jory Weintraub and Craig McClain	NESCent Education and Outreach and Science & Synthesis	Postdoctoral Professional Development Activity – Responsible Conduct of Research
5-June-09	Paula Spaeth	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	Fossils, Ecology, and Evolution
19-June-09	Vladimir Gapeyev and Xianhua Liu	NESCent Informatics	Will Work for Data! – Database Prototyping for Evolutionary Synthesis at

Appendix 9c: NESCent Seminar Series for Year 5

			NESCent
26-June-09	Jory Weintraub	NESCent Education and Outreach	Postdoctoral Professional Development Activity
28-Aug-09	Jory Weintraub	NESCent Education and Outreach	Postdoctoral Professional Development
4-Sept-09	Francisco Ubeda	University of Tennessee, NIMBioS	Multilocus Intragenomic Conflict and a Solution to the Recombination Hotspot Paradox
18-Sept-09	Hilmar Lapp and Todd Vision	NESCent Informatics	Everything You Ever Wanted to Know About NESCent Informatics
25-Sept-09	Gregor Yanega	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	Floating the Dodo: Patterns of Diversification in Island Birds (A Work in Progress)
9-Oct-09	Jonathon Payne	NESCent Working Group Leader, Stanford University, Department of Geology	Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology – Working Group Summary
16-Oct-09	Julie Meachen-Samuels	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	Carnivore Morphology and Evolution: Past, Present, and Future
23-Oct-09	Liam Revell	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	Ecology and Evolution of Tail Autotomy in Several Lizard Species
30-Oct-09	Robin Smith	NESCent Science Communications	Postdoctoral Professional Development: Communicating Your Science to the Media
6-Nov-09	Eric Schuettpelz	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	TBA
13-Nov-09	James Hunt	NESCent Sabbatical	TBA

Appendix 9c: NESCent Seminar Series for Year 5

		Scholar, North Carolina St Univ, Dept of Biology	
20-Nov-09	Benjamin Redelings	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	TBA

Appendix 9d: Outreach Activities of Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists at the Center

Meeting, Start Date-End Date, Location, Activities, *Attendees*

- **Society of Integrative and Comparative Biology 2009**, 1/3/09-1/7/09, Boston, MA, NESCent Information Booth, organized and coordinated NESCent luncheon/funding information session in collaboration with BioSynC, *Jory Weintraub, Kathleen Smith*
- **Plant and Animal Genome XVII**, 1/10/09-1/14/09, San Diego, CA, Organized workshop Database Tools for Evolutionary Genomics: An introduction to GMOD software for managing, *David Clements*
- **January 2009 GMOD Meeting**, 1/15/09-1/16/09, San Diego, CA, Presented about GMOD Help Desk and the state of the GMOD project, *David Clements*
- **University of Wisconsin Darwin Day**, 2/7/09, Madison, WI, NESCent Information Booth, *Kristin Jenkins*
- **Wisconsin Society of Science Teachers**, 3/5/09-3/7/09, Milwaukee, WI, Presentation on evolution education resources, *Kristin Jenkins*
- **Evolutionary Genetics - the impact of next generation sequencing technologies**, 4/2/09-4/4/09, Lutherstadt-Wittenberg, Germany, Presentation: "Visualizing and Integrating Next Generation Sequence Data using GMOD". *David Clements*
- **American Institute Biological Science**, 5/17/09-5/17/09, Washington, D.C., Board Meeting, *Joel Kingsolver, Robin Smith*
- **Meeting of the Technical Working Group for the Virtual Data Center**, 6/1/09-6/5/09, Albuquerque, NM, *Ryan Scherle*,
- **Society for Molecular Biology and Evolution**, 6/3/09-6/7/09, Iowa City, IA, Advertisement in conference program, attendance, talks, *David Clements, Todd Vision*
- **Next Generation Genome Analysis in Non-model Organisms. An American Genetic Association Special Event**, 6/11/09-6/13/09, Storrs, Connecticut, Presentation: "Seeing the forest and the trees: visualizing next generation sequence data", *David Clements*
- **Evolution 2009**, 6/12/09-6/14/09, Moscow, ID, NESCent Information Booth, Sponsorship of meeting, Poster: "Will work for data: Database prototyping for synthetic evolutionary research at NESCent", Co-organized the Evo 101 Teacher Workshop and participated in the SSE Education Committee meeting, Organized and Ran Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution 2009, Presentation: "Educational Resources from the National Evolutionary Synthesis Center" *Vladimir Gapeyev, Joel Kingsolver, Kristin Jenkins, Hilmar Lapp, Xianhua Liu, Craig McClain, Robin Smith, Todd Vision, Jory Weintraub*,
- **North American Paleontological Conference**, 6/21/09-6/26/09, Cincinnati, OH, Outreach and Presentation, *Craig McClain*
- **AAAS/NSF Vision and Change**, 7/15/09-7/17/09, Washington, DC, *Kristin Jenkins*
- **Southeast Regional meeting of DVM, Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology** 9/26/09, Chapel Hill, NC, Presentation of opportunities for funding at NESCent *Kathleen Smith*
- **European Society for Evolutionary Biology**, 9/24/09-9/27/09, Coordinated distribution of NESCent postcards at conference
- **SACNAS 2009**, 10/14/09-10/17/09, Dallas, TX, Organized and ran several outreach activities (field trip, mentoring session, scientific symposium, "Movie Night"), *Jory Weintraub*
- **National Association of Science Writers**, 10/16/09-10/22/09, Austin, TX, Attended writing & multimedia workshops, talked with freelance writers about ongoing research at NESCent, promoted NESCent's evolution blogging contest, *Robin Smith*
- **Kick-off meeting for the DataONE grant**, 10/19/09-10/23/09, Albuquerque, NM, *Ryan Scherle*
- **National Association of Science Teachers**, 10/29/09-10/30/09, Minneapolis, MN, Presentation on NESCent resources, *Kristin Jenkins*

Appendix 9d cont.: Outreach Activities of Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists at the Center

- **NABT 2009**, 11/10/09-11/14/09, Denver, CO, Organized and ran NABT Evolution symposium and workshop, NESCent Information Booth, Presentation "Educational Resources from NESCent", presented poster in Outreach Coordinators Section poster session, *Kristin Jenkins, Robin Smith, Brian Wiegmann, Jory Weintraub, Kathleen Smith*
- **Meeting of the Technical Working Group for the Virtual Data Center project**, 11/16/09-11/20/09, Knoxville, TN, Workshop: Comparative Genomics with GBrowse_syn: A hands on workshop for visualizing your syntenic data with GBrowse_syn, Poster: "P828: Managing Next Generation Sequence Data, *David Clement, Ryan Scherle*
- **NCSTA 2009**, 11/19/09, 11/20/09, Greensboro, NC, Worked NESCent booth, Presentation: "Evolution Education Resources from NESCent", *Jory Weintraub*

Appendix 10: NESCent Center Products (Publications, Software/Databases, Grants) for Year 5

Publications	
Long-term Sabbaticals	<p>Cronk, Q. (2009) <i>The Molecular Organography of Plants</i>. Oxford University Press.</p> <p>Nuismer, S. L., S. P. Otto, and F. Blanquart (2009) Host-parasite interactions and the evolution of non-random mating and parasite speciation. <i>Ecology Letters</i>. 11(9):937-946.</p>
Postdoctoral Fellows	<p>A. E. Zanne, M. Westoby, D. S. Falster, D. D. Ackerly, S. R. Loarie, S. E. J. Arnold, & D. A. Coomes. Angiosperm trait spectra: global variation in xylem anatomy and ecological function. <i>Nature</i>, submitted</p> <p>Bansal, M.S., J.G. Burleigh, O. Eulenstein, and D. Fernandez-Baca. Robinson-Foulds supertrees. <i>Algorithms for Molecular Biology</i>, in review</p> <p>Botero CA, Boogert NJ, Vehrencamp SL and Lovette IJ. (2009) Climatic Patterns Predict the Elaboration of Song Displays in Mockingbirds. <i>Current Biology</i> 19: 1-5.</p> <p>Burleigh J.G., Bansal M.S., Eulenstein O., and T.J. Vision. Inferring species trees using gene duplication episodes. <i>Molecular Biology and Evolution</i>, in review</p> <p>Chave, J., D. Coomes, S. Jansen, S. L. Lewis, N. G. Swenson, and A. E. Zanne. (2009) Towards a worldwide wood economics spectrum. <i>Ecology Letters</i> 12(4): 351-366.</p> <p>Collar, D.C., B.C. O'Meara, P.C. Wainwright, and T.J. Near. (2009) Piscivory limits diversification of feeding morphology in Centrarchid fishes. <i>Evolution</i>. 63(6):1557-1573.</p> <p>Collar, D. C., B. C. O'Meara, et al. (2009). Piscivory limits diversification of feeding morphology in centrarchid fishes. <i>Evolution</i> 63(6): 1557-1573.</p> <p>Cornwell, W. K., J. H. C. Cornelissen, S. D. Allison, P. Eggleton, C. Preston, F. Scarff, J. T. Weedon, C. Wirth, A. E. Zanne. (2009) Plant traits and wood fates across the globe: rotted, burned, or consumed? <i>Global Change Biology</i>. 15(10): 2431 - 2449.</p> <p>de Kort SR, Eldermire ERB, Valderrama S, Botero CA, and Vehrencamp SL. 2009. Trill consistency is an age-related assessment signal in banded wrens. <i>Proceedings of the Royal Society B</i> 276(1665): 2315-2321</p> <p>Dutheil, J., Ganapathy, G., Hobolth, A., Mailund, T., Uyenoyama, M. & Schierup, M. (2009). Ancestral Population Genomics: The Coalescent- Hidden Markov Model Approach. <i>Genetics</i>, in press.</p> <p>Ganapathy, G. and Uyenoyama, M. (2009). Site frequency spectra from genomic SNP surveys. <i>Theoretical Population Biology</i>, in press</p> <p>Hazkani-Covo E. (2009) Mitochondrial insertions into primate nuclear genomes suggest the use of numts as a tool for phylogeny. <i>Molecular Biology and Evolution</i>. 26(10):2175-2179.</p> <p>Heaney, L. R. and T. E. Roberts (2009). New perspectives on the long-term biogeographic dynamics and conservation of Philippine fruit bat. <i>Ecology, Evolution, and Conservation of Island Bats</i>. T. H. Fleming and P. A. Racey. Chicago, University of Chicago Press.</p> <p>Hereford, J. A. (2009) Quantitative Survey of Local Adaptation and Fitness Trade-offs. <i>American Naturalist</i> 173(5):579-588.</p> <p>Kimmel, C. B., B.L. Sidlauskas and Jennifer Clack. 2009. Linked morphological changes during palate evolution in early tetrapods. <i>Journal of Anatomy</i> 215: 91-109</p> <p>Lajeunesse, M. A. (2009). Meta-analysis and the comparative phylogenetic method. <i>The American Naturalist</i> 174(3): 369-381.</p>

McCall, L.W. (2009) Studying cultural evolution at the tips: Human cross-cultural ecology. *Evolution: Education and Outreach* 2: 1936-6426

McCall, L.W. (2009) Cultural adaptations after progressionism. *Cross-Cultural Research* 43: 62-89.

McCall, L.W. (2009) The comparative biology of cultural inheritance. *Evolution: Education and Outreach* 2: 573-574.

Moore, B. R., **S. A. Smith**, R. H. Ree, and M. J. Donoghue. (2009) Incorporating fossil data in biogeographic inference: a likelihood approach. *Evolution*, in press

O'Meara, B.C. (2009) A new heuristic method for joint species delimitation and species tree inference. *Systematic Biology*, in press

Roberts, T. E., T. Davenport, et al. (2009). The biogeography of introgression in the critically endangered African monkey *Rungwecebus kipunji*. *Biology Letters*, in press

Roberts, T.E., E.J. Sargis, and L.E. Olson. (2009) Networks, trees, and treeshrews: Assessing support and identifying conflict with multiple loci and a problematic root. *Systematic Biology* 58: 257-270.

Roberts, T. E., E. J. Sargis, et al. (2009). Networks, trees, and treeshrews: assessing support and identifying conflict with multiple loci and a problematic root. *Systematic Biology* 58(2): 257-270.

Sidlauskas, B. L. (200) Parallel morphological and ecological diversification in African and South American characiform fishes, *The American Naturalist*, submitted

Sidlauskas, B., Ganapathy, G., Price, S., Hazkani-Covo, E., McCall, L.W., Spaeth, P., Jenkins, KP., Scherle, R., Lapp, H., Kidd, DM. Big ideas, big data: The role of synthesis in evolutionary biology. *Evolution*, in press.

Sidlauskas, B. L. (2009) A supermatrix-based phylogeny for the Anostomoidea (Pisces: Characiformes). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, in review

Sidlauskas, B. L., J. Mol and R. P. Vari. (2009) Traditional morphometric, geometric and meristic approaches to species discrimination and allometry in the *Leporinus cylindricus* group (Characiformes: Anostomidae), with a description of a new species from Suriname. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, in review

Smith, S. A., J. M. Beaulieu, and M. J. Donoghue. 2009. Mega-phylogeny approach for comparative biology: an alternative to supertree and supermatrix approaches. *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 9:37.

Smith, S. A. and J. M. Beaulieu (2009). Life-history influences rates of climatic niche evolution in flowering plants. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*, in press

Smith, S. A. (2009). Taking into account phylogenetic and divergence-time uncertainty in a parametric biogeographical analysis of the Northern Hemisphere plant clade Caprifoliaceae. *Journal of Biogeography*, in press

Smith, S. A., R. H. Ree, and M. J. Donoghue. (2009) Accuracy of maximum-likelihood inferences of geographic range reconstructions and parameter estimates: a simulation study. *Systematic Biology*, in press

Spaeth, P. A. 2009. Morphological convergence and coexistence in three sympatric North American species of *Microtus* (Rodentia:Arvicolinae). *Journal of Biogeography* 36:350-361.

Spaeth, P. A., M. van Tuinen, Y. L. Chan, D. Terca, and E. A. Hadly. 2009. Phylogeography of *Microtus longicaudus* in the tectonically and glacially dynamic landscape of the Central Rocky Mountains. *Journal of Mammalogy* 90:571-584.

Weedon, J., W. Cornwell, H. Cornelissen, **A. E. Zanne**, C. Wirth, and D. Coomes. (2009) Global meta-analysis of wood decomposition rates: the role of wood traits. *Ecology Letters*. 12(1):45-56.

Short-term Visitors	Santini F, Harmon LJ, Carnevale G, Alfaro M. (2009) Did genome duplication drive the origin of teleosts? A comparative study of diversification in ray-finned fishes. <i>BMC Evolutionary Biology</i> 9
Working Groups	Alfaro ME, Santini F, Brock CD, Alamillo H, Dornburg A, Carnevale G, Rabosky D, Harmon LJ. (2009) Nine exceptional radiations plus high turnover explain species diversity in jawed vertebrates. <i>Proceedings of National Academy of Science, U.S.A.</i> 106(32):13410-13414.
	Antonelli, A., and I. Sanmartin. Reconstructing the spatio-temporal evolution of the ancient angiosperm genus <i>Hedyosmum</i> (Chloranthaceae) using empirical and simulated approaches. <i>Systematic Biology</i> , in press
	Booth MG and Hoeksema JD (2009). Mycorrhizal networks ameliorate effects of canopy trees on seedling survival. <i>Ecology</i> , submitted
	Buckley, L et al. (2009) A quantitative comparison of correlative and mechanistic species' distribution models. <i>Ecology Letters</i> , submitted
	Byars, S., D. Ewbank, et al. (2009). Natural selection in a contemporary human population. <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, U.S.A.</i> , in press
	Druzinsky, R., S.H. Williams, N. Konow et al. Special issue of <i>Journal of Experimental Zoology</i> concerning an update on methods of data collection and analysis for electromyographic data on feeding. Submission: June, 2010
	Faith, D., C. Lozuone, et al. (2009). The Cladistic Basis for the PD (Phylogenetic Diversity) Measure Links Evolutionary Features to Environmental Gradients and Supports Broad Applications of Microbial Ecology's "Phylogenetic beta diversity" Framework. <i>International Journal of Molecular Sciences</i> 10:139-156
	Fritsch, P. W., S. R. Manchester, R. D. Stone, and F. Almeda (2009) Biogeographic patterns support a boreotropical origin for the amphi-Pacific tropical disjunct flowering plant family <i>Symplocaceae</i> . <i>American Journal of Botany</i> , submitted
	Gilman, S. et al. (2009) The great unknown: community interactions under climate change. <i>Trends in Recent Ecology and Evolution</i> , submitted
	Goodwillie, C., Sargent, R. D., Moeller, D. A., Ree, R., Cheptou, P. O., Eckert, C. G., Elle, E., Geber, M. A., Johnston, M. O., Kalisz, S., Kelly, J. K., Porcher, E., Vallejo-Marin, M., and A. A. Winn (2009) Correlated evolution of mating system and floral display traits in flowering plants and its implications for the distribution of mating system variation. <i>New Phytologist</i> , in press
	Harmon, L. J., J. B. Losos, J. Davies, R. G. Gillespie, J. L. Gittleman, W. B. Jennings, K. Kozak, M. A. McPeck, F. Moreno-Roarck, T. J. Near, A. Purvis, R. E. Ricklefs, D. Schluter, J. A. Schulte II, O. Seehausen, B. Sidlauskas, O.R. Torres-Carvajal, J. T. Weir, & A. Mooers. (2009). Body size and shape rarely evolve in early bursts. <i>Evolution</i> , in reviews
	Harris, A. J, Q.Y. (J) Xiang and D. Thomas (2009) Molecular and morphological inference of the phylogeny, origin, and biogeographic history of <i>Aesculus</i> L. (<i>Sapindaceae</i> or <i>Hippocastanaceae</i>). <i>TAXON</i> , in press
	Hickerson, M.J., B.C. Carstens, J. Cavender-Bares, K.A. Crandall, C.H. Graham, J. Johnson, L. Rissler, P.F. Victoriano, and A.D. Yoder. 20 years after Avise et al. 1987: Comparative phylogeography fulfilling original promise by integrating with emerging fields. <i>Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution</i> , in press
	Hoeksema JD, Chaudhary VB, Gehring CA, Johnson NC, Karst J, Koide RT, Pringle A, Zabinski C, Bever JD, Moore JC, Wilson GWT, Klironomos JN, and Umbanhowar J. Context-dependency in plant response to mycorrhizal fungi: A meta-analysis. <i>Ecology</i> , submitted

	Johnston, M.O., E. Porcher, P.-O. Cheptou, C.G. Eckert, E. Elle, M.A. Geber, S. Kalisz, J.K. Kelly, D.A. Moeller, M. Vallejo-Marin, A. A. Winn (2009) Correlations among fertility components can maintain mixed mating in plants. <i>American Naturalist</i> 73: 1-11.
	Lacey, E. P., M. B. Lovin, et al. (2010). "Floral reflectance, color and thermoregulation: What really explains geographic variation in thermal acclimation ability in ectotherms? <i>The American Naturalist</i> , in press
	Lahti, D. C., N. A. Johnson, et al. (2009). Relaxed selection in the wild. <i>Trends in Recent Ecology and Evolution</i> 24(9): 487-496.
	Li, M., J. Li, J. Jiang, C. Fu, and W. Judd. (2009) Phylogenetics and Biogeography of <i>Pieris</i> (Lyonieae, Ericaceae): inferred from sequences of nuclear and chloroplast genomes. <i>Systematic Botany</i> 34(3):553-560.
	Manchester, S.R., Q.Y. (J) Xiang, T.M. Kodrul, and M. Akhmetiev. (2009) Leaves of <i>Cornus</i> (Cornaceae) from the Paleocene of North America and Asia confirmed by trichome characters. <i>International Journal of Plant Sciences</i> . 170(1):132-142.
	Moore, B. A. and M. J. Donoghue. (2009) Evaluating the impact of historical events on rates of diversification: A Bayesian approach using cross-validation predictive densities. <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Science, U.S.A.</i> 106(11):4307-4312.
	Payne, J.L., Boyer, A.G., Brown, J.H., Finnegan, S., Kowaleski, M., Krause, R.A., Lyons, S.k., McClain, C.R., McShea, D.W., Novack-Gottshall, P.M., Smith, F.A., Stempien, J.A., Wang, S.C. (2009) Two-phase increase in the maximum size of life over 3.5 billion years reflects biological innovation and environmental opportunity. <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Science, U.S.A.</i> 106(1):24-27
	Porcher, E., J. K. Kelly, P-O. Cheptou, C.G. Eckert, M.O. Johnston, S. Kalisz (2009) The genetic consequences of fluctuating inbreeding depression and the evolution of plant mating systems. <i>Journal of Evolutionary Biology</i> . 22(4):708-717.
	Prosdocimi, F., B. Chisham, E. Pontelli, J.D. Thompson, and A. Stoltzfu. (2009) Initial Implementation of a Comparative Data Analysis Ontology. <i>Evolutionary Bioinformatics</i> . 5:47-56.
	Ree, R. H., and I. Sanmartin (2009) Guest Editorial: Prospects and challenges for parametric models in historical biogeographical inference. <i>Journal of Biogeography</i> . 36(7):1211-1220.
	Renner, S. S., G. W. Grimm, G. Schneeweiss, T. F. Stuessy, and R. E. Ricklefs. 2008. Rooting and dating maples (<i>Acer</i>) with an uncorrelated-rates molecular clock: Implications for North American/Asian disjunctions. <i>Systematic Biology</i> . 57(5): 795-808.
	Richards, C.L., O. Bossdorf, and M. Pigliucci. What role does heritable epigenetic variation play in phenotypic evolution? <i>Bioscience</i> , in press
	Vallejo-Marin, M., M. Uyenoyama, P.-O. Cheptou, C.G. Eckert, E. Elle, M.A. Geber, C. Goodwillie, M.O. Johnston, S. Kalisz, J.K. Kelly, D.A. Moeller, E. Porcher, R.H. Ree, R.D. Sargent, M. Vallejo-Marin, A.A. Winn. (2009) Clonality, population structure and inbreeding depression, in prep
	Volz, S. M., and S. S. Renner. (2009) Phylogeography of the ancient Eurasian medicinal plant genus <i>Bryonia</i> (Cucurbitaceae) inferred from nuclear and chloroplast sequences. <i>TAXON</i> . 58(2):550-560.
Education and Outreach Groups	Catley, K. M., & Novick, L. R. (2009). Seeing the Wood for the Trees: An Analysis of Evolutionary Diagrams in Biology Textbooks. <i>BioScience</i> , in press
	Jenkins, K. (2009) Evolution in Biology Education: Sparking Imaginations and Supporting Learning. <i>Evolution: Education and Outreach</i> 2(3):347-348
	O'Brien, D.T., Wilson, D.S., Hawley, P.H. (2009) "Evolution for Everyone": A Course that Expands Evolutionary Theory Beyond the Biological Sciences.

	Evolution: Education and Outreach 2(3):445-457
	Smith, J.J. and Cheruvilil, K.S. (2009) Using Inquiry and Tree-Thinking to "March Through the Animal Phyla": Teaching Introductory Comparative Biology in an Evolutionary Context. <i>Evolution: Education and Outreach</i> 2(3):429-444
	Speth, E.B., Long, T.M., Pennock, R.T., Ebert-May, D. (2009) Using Avida-ED for Teaching and Learning About Evolution in Undergraduate Introductory Biology Courses. <i>Evolution: Education and Outreach</i> 2(3):415-428
	Thanukos, A. (2009) From Newsroom to Classroom. <i>Evolution: Education and Outreach</i> 2(3):533-537
	Wall, C. E., S. H. Williams, C. J. Vinyard, R. Z. German, S. W. Herring, G. Langenbach, D. Lieberman, W. L. Hylander, A. W. (2010) A Review of Mammalian Feeding. <i>Archives of Oral Biology</i> , invited submission
Submitted Grants	
Working Groups	Buckley, L. and M. Angilletta. Mechanistic range models for changing environments: using species' traits to consider adaptation and biotic constraints. NSF and DOE National Institute for Climate Change Research.
	Cellinese, Cranston, Lapp, MacKay, Pontelli and Stoltzfus. July, 2009. INTEROP: A network for enabling community-driven standards to link evolution into the global web of data (EvoIO). NSF INTEROP program, \$250,000 per year total costs.
	Pontelli, Gupta and Stoltzfus. Development of an Enabling Infrastructure for Evolutionary Comparative Analysis. Proposal for 2-year NIH ARRA funding.
	Research Coordination Network proposal submitted July 23, 2009. EDEN (Evo-Devo-Eco Network): A research coordination network to promote technique and community development across the Evo-Devo-Eco
	C. E. Wall, R. Z. German, C. J. Vinyard, and S. H. Williams Date: August 11, 2009 Title: COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH: The Feeding Experiments End-user Database (FEED): An open-access database for integrated evolutionary analyses of mammalian feeding. Amount: \$936,486 Sponsor: National Science Foundation (Advances in Bioinformatics) Status: Pending
Education Working Groups	Uno, G. Preparing to Prepare the 21st Century Biology Student: Using Scientific Societies as Change Agents for the Introductory Biology Experience. Research Collaborative Network Grant
Center	Extending and Enhancing Understanding Evolution for the Undergraduate Community, NSF CCLI program. Co-PI with PI R. Caldwell (University of California Berkeley).
Software & Databases	
Working Groups	Mammalian Feeding Apparatus Database (in development) Mammalian Feeding Apparatus Working Group. National Evolutionary Synthesis Center. http://feeding-dev.nescent.org/
	Maximum Size Database (2009) Phanerozoic Body Size Trends through Time and Space Working Group. National Evolutionary Synthesis Center. http://bodysize.nescent.org/
	Primate Life History Database (2009) Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories Working Group National Evolutionary Synthesis Center. http://plhdb/nescent.org/plhdb
	Visual Ecology and Visual System Morphology Database (in development) Evolutionary Shifts in Vertebrate Visual Ecology and Visual System Morphology Working Group. National Evolutionary Synthesis Center

Appendix 10 cont.: NESCent Center Products (Publications, Software/Databases, Grants) for Year 5

Hosted Meetings	Wieczorek, J., Constable, H and Russell, L. (2009) VertNet Portal.
Informatics Working Group	Scherle, R. & Bapat, A. Source code for the Dryad data repository. http://dryad.googlecode.com

NESCent Staff Chart – end of year 5

